

Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automation Road Transport

HEADSTART D.1.4 Functional requirements of selected use cases

Work package	WP1: Use cases and requirements
Task	Task 1.4: Functional requirements and use case selection
Deliverable Lead	SAF
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Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Status	Final
Due date	30/09/2019
Document date	10/10/2019
Version number	1.0
	<i>This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824309.</i>

PARTNERS

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Revision and history chart

Version	Date	Main author	Summary of changes
0.1	24/06/2019	Robert Hult	Draft outline
0.2	12/08/2019	Robert Hult	Update to draft outline, added detailed comments on what is expected from contributors in T1.4 with examples
0.3	16/08/2019	Robert Hult	Added example and template for partner input on Chapter 3
0.4	22/08/2019	Robert Hult	Added additional explanations in Section 1.4.8 on contributions to requirements.
0.5	09/19/2019	Martin Skoglund	Outline draft cleaned
0.6	12/09/2019	Martin Skoglund	Added contributions to chapter 2 and 3 from VEDECOM, ICCS and VIF.
0.7	13/09/2019	Mats Jonasson	Added contributions to chapter 2 and 3 from BAST, ICCS, IKA and Vicomtech
0.8	16/09/2019	Martin Skoglund	Updated intro and integrated more input.
0.9	17/09/2019	Mats Jonasson	Updated abbreviations, glossary and references
0.91	20/09/2019	Mats Jonasson	Added 1.3 and 2.7
0.92	23/09/2019	Martin Skoglund	Updated Chapter 1,2,3,4,5. Released for review.
0.93	03/10/2019	Anders Thorsén	Repaired damaged document. V219 in Box, dated 01/10/2019, used as base and manual update made to match V228 in Box dated 03/10/19. Revision changed to 0.10.0 to try to follow structure in this table.
0.94	07/10/2019	Martin Skoglund	Minor adjustments.
1.0	08/10/2019	Martin Skoglund	Final version.
1.0	09/10/2019	Álvaro Arrúe	Final check of the project coordinator

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Glossary of terms

Term	Description
Use Case [SOTIF]	Specification of a generalized field of application, possibly entailing the following information about the system: one or several scenarios; the functional range; the desired behavior; and the system boundaries. (The use case description typically does not include a detailed list of all relevant scenarios for this use case. Instead a more abstract description of these scenarios is used.)
Scenario [SAE]	Abstraction and general description of a temporal and spatial traffic constellation without any specification of the parameters.
Scene [SAE]	Snapshot that includes the moving and non-moving elements of the traffic environment, the self-representation of all actors and observers and the relations between those elements.
Logical scenario [SAE]	Beginning with an initial scene, a model of the time sequence of scenes whose parameters are defined as ranges; at a defined point in time, the behavior of the main actor (vehicle under test) is not further specified.
Attack	Attempt to destroy, expose, alter, disable, steal or gain unauthorized access to or make unauthorized use of an asset [ISO 27000:2018]
Availability	The proportion of time a system is in a functioning condition
Concrete scenario [SAE]	A concrete scenario represents a parameterised model of the temporal sequence of scenes (logical scenario), which begins with a concrete start scene. From a defined point in time, the behaviour of the main actor (ego-vehicle) is not further specified, so that the outcome is hypothetical, but all other influencing factors are defined in advance.
Driver	A user who performs in real-time part or all of the dynamic driving task (DDT) and/or DDT fallback for a particular vehicle.

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
AD	Automated Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
ADS	Automated Driving System
BMWi	Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (Germany)
CA	Consortium agreement
CAD	Connected and Automated Driving (function)
CIPV	Closest in Path Vehicle
DDT	Dynamic Driving Task
EDR	Event Data Recorder
ERTRAC	European Road Transport Research Advisory Council
EV	Electric Vehicles
ESC	Electronic Stability Control
FOTs	Field Operational Tests
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRVA	Working Party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles
HEADSTART	Harmonised European Solutions for Testing Automated Road Transport
HiL	Hardware in the Loop
IoT	Internet of Things
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KETs	Key Enabling Technologies
MRM	Minimum Risk Manoeuvre
NDS	National Data and Surveying Services
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
OD	Operational Domain
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEDR	Object Event Detection and Response
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
RSU	Road Side Unit
SAE	Society of Automotive Engineers
SiL	Software in the Loop
SOTIF	Safety Of The Intended Functionality
TARA	Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment
UN	United Nations
ViL	Vehicle in the loop
VUT	Vehicle under Test
VRU	Vulnerable Road Users
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report presents use cases enabling testing and validation of Connected and Automated Driving (CAD). Chapter 2 lists the various requirements deemed necessary to fulfil in order to validate and demonstrate the HEADSTART methodology. Chapter 3 describes the use cases with the resources necessary. The use cases are assessed in Chapter 3 and prioritized in Chapter 4.

To validate and demonstrate the HEADSTART methodology it will be applied to up to four use cases. It important to choose these use cases judiciously. To provide the best informational foundation for that selection is the purpose of this deliverable.

	Truck Platooning	Highway Pilot	Traffic Jam Chauffeur	Valet Parking	Urban Automated Shuttle
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements on testability of positioning in HEADSTART	4.5				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements on testability of communication in HEADSTART	3.5				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements of testability of cyber-security in HEADSTART	3.7				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding physical testing in HEADSTART	2.9				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding proving-ground testing in HEADSTART	2.6				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding field operational tests in HEADSTART	3.1				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding model-based testing in HEADSTART	3.6				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding definition and availability of scenarios in HEADSTART	2.6				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding requirements on collaboration partners in HEADSTART	2.6				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to OEMs and Tier1's in HEADSTART.	3.3				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to type-approval authorities in HEADSTART	2.9				
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to consumer testing in HEADSTART	1.7				
Total Average Score	3.7	3.8	3.2	3.5	3.1

FIGURE 1: USE CASES SUITABILITY RANKING FOR EACH HEADSTART REQUIREMENT CATEGORY.

The suitability ranking presented in Figure 1 is based on the information collected in Deliverable 1.3 and 1.4. and converted to a ranking by the partners in the HEADSTART. For each HEADSTART requirement category, there is a corresponding ranking for each use case and also an aggregation to a total result, which can be used as a basis for a future selection of use cases.

1 Introduction

HEADSTART will define testing and validation procedures for CAD functions including its key enabling technologies (KET); communication, cyber-security and positioning. Several use cases must be defined to do so.

1.1 Background

The purpose of the HEADSTART project is harmonization of existing testing and validation approaches. The project will develop, validate and demonstrate a methodology for testing and validation of CAD which build upon existing initiatives; but will also include testing and validation of three identified KETs (communication, positioning and cyber-security). A scenario-based approach is used, methodology for the whole toolchain, from input data to testing itself to validation. Moreover, the main goal is the harmonization of existing other efforts in the area. The project aims to develop procedures to identify which scenarios to test and on what testing platform such tests should be performed. The whole toolchain from input data to testing and validation is included. As they are the most expensive and time consuming to perform, procedures to select which scenarios should be selected for physical testing will be developed, based on a measure of representativeness of the scenario.

The overall concept of HEADSTART as described in the application is shown in Figure 2. Building from existing scenario descriptions for CAD functions, that are currently under development in other initiatives, HEADSTART will enhance them by including Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, positioning and cyber-security. HEADSTART will include KETs in the generally accepted scenario creation and definition process and address user group specific requirements that have impact on the scenario descriptions.

FIGURE 2: HEADSTART CONCEPT BASED ON THE PEGASUS APPROACH (SIMPLIFICATION) [1].

Appendix 1 in the HEADSTART Grant Agreement identifies four preselected use cases as shown in Figure 3. The aim is not to perform validation of all use cases currently available, but rather to demonstrate that the methodology is robust, reliable and flexible enough to adapt to different use cases. It is proposed to map the foreseen Automated Driving System (ADS) features in ERTRAC CAD Roadmap 2019 [2] with the preselected use cases in Figure 3 **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** and use this as basis for the further evaluation of the KETs.

FIGURE 3: HEADSTART PRESELECTED USE CASES [1, ANNEX 1].

The priority use cases identified from user groups in Task 1.2 and candidates for demonstration in HEADSTART WP4 are listed below with SAE Level as defined in SAE J3016 [3]. Listed are also projects considered relevant for HEADTSTART including involved partners.

- For passenger cars
 - Highway Pilot (SAE Level 4)
 - Traffic Jam Chauffeur (SAE Level 3)
 - Valet Parking (SAE Level 4)
- For freight vehicles
 - Truck Platooning (SAE Level 4)
- For urban mobility vehicles
 - Urban Automated Shuttle (SAE Level 4)

In order to validate and demonstrate the methodology, HEADSTART will apply it to up to four use cases. It is therefore important that these use cases are representative enough for this purpose. For instance, the use cases should allow both physical and model-based testing, as well as testing of the identified KETs. Moreover, since it is not within the scope of HEADSTART to define new use cases nor to develop new technology, they must be selected such that relevant resources for both their description (e.g. Operational Design Domain (ODD) definitions, functional requirements) and the validation and demonstration of the methodology (e.g. driving functions, scenarios, prototype vehicles) are available from external sources.

1.2 Purpose and scope

The purpose of this deliverable is two-fold:

The first purpose is to assess the relevance of proposed use cases in the context of the project by investigating if they are, e.g.,

1. representative enough to validate and demonstrate a complete methodology with regards to the all requirement categories in HEADSTART;
2. relies on mature technology, where the relevant resources can be made available to HEADSTART; and

3. are relevant for the key user groups (OEMs & Tiers, Type Approval and Consumer Testing organizations).

The deliverable will provide a description of a number of use cases and an assessment of their qualities with respect to the above-mentioned requirements as well as others. The assessed use cases will be ranked in order of suitability for HEADSTART, and compiled to a list from which the final use case(s) will be selected at *Milestone 3 – Use Case Selected* (M11/M12)

The second purpose is to, for each use case, identify where relevant resources for developing, validating and demonstrating the HEADSTART methodology can be found. This includes scenarios and functional requirements, and identification of potential projects to collaborate with. This information will serve as a resource to later work packages.

1.3 Approach

The approach taken to arrive at the ranked list is the following:

1. Identify and compile the requirements that a use case must fulfil to demonstrate the HEADSTART methodology
2. Starting from the list of use cases indicated as priorities in the surveys and interviews produced in *Task 1.2 – Stakeholders and user group needs*, compile a detailed description of each use case including
 - a. A description of the use case
 - b. A list of available resources, including projects that cover the use case and their status
3. Assess each use case in terms of its ability to meet the requirements identified for the project
4. Compile the assessments of the use cases and rank them in terms of suitability for HEADSTART

As neither use case definitions nor technology will be developed within HEADSTART, the approach taken to compile the resources will be conducting a review of the available work done for each different use case.

2 Requirements on use cases in HEADSTART

The general descriptions of the requirements are listed in this chapter and shows the various requirements deemed necessary to fulfil in order to validate and demonstrate the HEADSTART methodology. The specific requirements are, for traceability reasons, kept in an Excel file which is also a major part of the input to chapter 4. Some of these could be seen as “functional requirements” on the use cases themselves from the perspective of HEADSTART. An example could be that some functions of a use case must utilize wireless communication to make sure that the methodology covers this KET. Another example could be that the use case must contain scenarios feasible to be physically tested on most proving grounds.

The requirements on the use cases of this chapter (chapter 2) are then compared to the list of use cases (chapter 3). The use cases are assessed (chapter 3) and prioritized (chapter 4). (See Figure 4jError! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.)

FIGURE 4: INFORMATIONAL FOUNDATION FOR THE USE CASE SELECTION

2.1 Requirements on testability of the KETs

2.1.1 Positioning

The aspect that should be testable is the ability of an actor in the traffic system to decide its own position. This is done by comparing and evaluating the residual between the actual and ground truth position of the actor's test objects.

Testability of positioning concerns the position of test objects such as the ego vehicle and the surroundings e.g. static objects such as landmarks, and dynamic ones, such as other vehicles, pedestrians etc. Testing the position means to measure the absolute or relative position. Absolute position is the position relative to a global reference frame which has its orientation and origin fixed to earth, e.g. by using Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) including the American Global Positioning System (GPS), the European Galileo system, the Russian GLONASS system or the Chinese Beidou system. Relative position is defined as the distance between the test object and another object, e.g. the road markers, road shoulders, etc.

Position is measured in two or a three-dimensional space. If two dimensions, the most common representation is to measure position in the horizontal plane, which is orthogonal to gravity or to the road plane. With three dimensions, it is common to add a vertical dimension admitting height position to be tested. The unit for position varies, but the most common are meter and degrees. GNSS measures for example the position in spherical coordinates by the degrees of latitude and longitude and the height in meters from the seas surface. The latitude and longitude could in turn be projected (flattened) to a Cartesian coordinate system with x and y axis using meter as the unit.

Standalone GNSS precision varies from 15 to 1 meters, but it varies depending on number of satellite in sight, obstacles between the satellite signal and the receiving antenna and the presence of interferences or other disturbances. More sophisticated GNSS receivers (able to resolve the GNSS ambiguities keeping into account both carriers phased and pseudo range measurements) can achieve up to 1-2 centimeters accuracy in optimal conditions. Such a performance can be achieved in larger testing environments combining the GNSS output with either odometry or inertial measurement units. The high precision issue is one of the main challenges to be addressed in the certification and homologation activities for L4 and L5 CAD functionalities.

There are also tests that could not rely on GNSS. Such tests are for example performed indoors or without line of sight to GNSS satellites. Valet parking is one use case that typically could require such tests. Indoor positioning of objects and the vehicle should be possible to perform up to a satisfying degree. Laser or radar-based instrumentation available to measure the relative distance with cm-mm precision to a reference point.

Two important aspects on measuring position is the update frequency (sampling rate) and the time delay. If update frequency is too slow and/or time delay too long, the positioning risks to be irrelevant since the measured

data do not represent ground truth position for an intended time or/and space domain. This will be important for driving at high speed, e.g. highway driving, where large position errors could be expected.

Another important aspect is to measure the position along with the position uncertainty. The uncertainty information gives information if the position error is acceptable or not. Using GNSS, the quantity dilution of precision is estimated by the GNSS receiver. This entity indicates the uncertain radius around the expected position. Too large dilution of precision means that the measured position likely has large error, resulting in a risk for position irrelevancy.

2.1.2 Communication

V2X communication includes all type of potential communication among actors in the future traffic environment, such as vehicles, pedestrians, infrastructure or other road-side-units (RSUs). Explicit testing which would lead to verification of such great variety of communication systems and parameters is not affordable in terms of time and cost, thus a communication categorization of testing shall be applied. Latency and reliability can be tested via function, performance and protocol conformance testing, while communication-based security may be granted through gateway, penetration and accelerated testing (Figure 5).

Conformance testing: Protocol conformance is of vital importance to ensure interoperability among the different participants. The protocols may be categorized into communications and security protocol, dealing with V2X communication and certification/authentication processes correspondingly.

Function testing: Application function testing can be conducted either in the laboratory or on field, to determine whether an application can be triggered in several scenarios. In practice this is feasible through simulation techniques, considering real and non-real time parameters.

Performance testing: It includes end-to-end communication delay testing, processing speed, packet delivery success transfer rate testing, network bandwidth and throughput, workload efficiency and reliability and parameter testing, such as signal strength under different channels. Through performance testing, testers can understand the effects of basic network communications, and further determine whether the performance of network communications can support V2X applications.

Vehicle gateway testing: the testing of the vehicle gateway consists of the system under test (vehicle gateways, in-vehicle wired and wireless devices, networks, service platforms) and the testing system, which is interconnected as shown in Figure 5.

FIGURE 5: VEHICLE GATEWAY TESTING ARCHITECTURE [4]

Accelerated testing: It can be used in lab simulations, human-in-the-loop tests with driving simulators, hardware-in-the-loop tests, or field testing, to test the reliability of the V2X in working conditions such as heavy rain, fog, and other extreme weather, and the network communications performance during traffic jams.

2.1.3 Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity, standards and methods for automated vehicles

Cybersecurity is seen as a prerequisite for safety rather than an enabling technology. Without cybersecurity, the safety of the vehicle cannot be guaranteed. Some of the cyber security requirements are dependent on the initial design phases of the CAD functions and therefore not clearly part of the simulation and/or physical testing of automated vehicles.

Within HEADSTART, cybersecurity is therefore covered with following actions:

1. Definition of a pre-requisite check list prior to proving ground and field trial testing
2. Identification of threats and vulnerabilities list and a definition on how to introduce them in the test cases considering its potential effects
3. Mapping of threats with AD functions and key enabling technologies
4. Decision to make proving ground tests from the malfunction point of view

With this approach we address cybersecurity from a design point of view and place the issue in the area of general testing methodology developed in the project, as if it is another key enabling technology such as positioning or communication.

In order to treat cybersecurity in a common way across OEMs and suppliers, common practices and standards can or need to be followed. These are:

- SAE J3061 – “Cybersecurity Guidebook for Cyber-physical vehicle systems” [5]. SAE J3061 is published by SAE as a practical guide for vehicle cybersecurity. Published in January 2016, the 128-page guidebook describes a framework for ensuring the information security of a product over its entire life cycle (from development to decommissioning) and provides an overview of cybersecurity methods. SAE J3061 is a guidebook and not a standard, therefore its application is not binding to developers of vehicles. It is also targeted to vehicles in general and does not relate to automated vehicles, that are a subset therein.

- ISO/SAE 21434 "Road vehicles - Cybersecurity engineering" [6] is a standard under development for cyber security of vehicles. It is expected to be published in 2020, the current status within ISO is a Committee Draft (CD, as of August 2019), i.e. some of the details describe may still change. The standard is developed jointly by a working group of ISO and SAE and will be approved by both organisations.

Currently there are no standards or common practices for the narrower field of cybersecurity in automated driving. Concerning automated driving, there is the standard ISO PAS 21448: Road Vehicles – “Safety Of The Intended Functionality” (SOTIF) [7]. However, this standard mostly aims at providing safety in case of distorted sensor data, but not security incidents that may have the same implications.

Cybersecurity testing within these standards highly depends on actions to be done in the design phase of a vehicle or vehicle function. One very important analysis in this aspect is the Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) activity to be carried out as part of the cybersecurity lifecycle. TARA is mentioned in SAE J3061 as well as in ISO/SAE 21434. TARA itself can be performed with different methods, e.g.

- HEAVENS (HEA ling Vulnerabilities to Enhance Software Security)
- EVITA (EVITA: E-Safety Vehicle Intrusion Protected Applications)
- OCTAVE (Operational Critical Threat, Asset and Vulnerability Evaluation)
- TVRA (Threat, Vulnerabilities, and implementation Risks Analysis)

or combinations of them. Figure 6. gives a graphical overview of these methods. Further information on applying TARA can be found in [8].

FIGURE 6: THREAT ANALYSIS & RISK ASSESSMENT (TARA) METHODS MENTIONED IN J3061

Cyber-security requirements - Key cyber threats

Automated vehicles are prone to many different threats. These threats can be grouped in many ways. It is important that you can systematically cover all threats and that you do not risk of missing some. Therefore, HEADSTART will follow standardized cybersecurity threat catalogues available in literature.

One compilation of threats has been compiled by the UN Task Force on Cyber Security and Over-the-Air Issues of the Working Party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles (GRVA) within the World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations (WP.29). The following list shows the 32 key cyber threats from the draft recommendation [9] of this working group.

TABLE 1: THREATS REGARDING BACK-END SERVERS

Category: Threats regarding back-end servers:	
Threat 1	Back-end servers used as a means to attack a vehicle or extract data
Threat 2	Services from back-end server being disrupted, affecting the operation of a vehicle
Threat 3	Data held on back-end servers being lost or compromised (“data breach”)

TABLE 2: THREATS TO VEHICLES REGARDING THEIR COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Category: Threats to vehicles regarding their communication channels:	
Threat 4	Spoofing of messages or data received by the vehicle
Threat 5	Communication channels used to conduct unauthorized manipulation, deletion or other amendments to vehicle held code/data
Threat 6	Communication channels permit untrusted/unreliable messages to be accepted or are vulnerable to session hijacking/replay attacks
Threat 7	Information can be readily disclosed. For example, through eavesdropping on communications or through allowing unauthorized access to sensitive files or folders
Threat 8	Denial of service attacks via communication channels to disrupt vehicle functions
Threat 9	An unprivileged user is able to gain privileged access to vehicle systems
Threat 10	Viruses embedded in communication media are able to infect vehicle systems
Threat 11	Messages received by the vehicle (for example X2V or diagnostic messages), or transmitted within it, contain malicious content

TABLE 3: THREATS TO VEHICLES REGARDING THEIR UPDATE PROCEDURES

Category: Threats to vehicles regarding their update procedures:	
Threat 12	Misuse or compromise of update procedures
Threat 13	It is possible to deny legitimate updates

TABLE 4: THREATS TO VEHICLES REGARDING UNINTENDED HUMAN ACTIONS

Category: Threats to vehicles regarding unintended human actions:	
Threat 14	Misconfiguration of equipment or systems by legitimate actor, e.g. owner or maintenance community
Threat 15	Legitimate actors are able to take actions that would unwittingly facilitate a cyber-attack

TABLE 5: THREATS TO VEHICLES REGARDING THEIR EXTERNAL CONNECTIVITY AND CONNECTIONS

Category: Threats to vehicles regarding their external connectivity and connections:

Threat 16	Manipulation of the connectivity of vehicle functions enables a cyber-attack, this can include telematics; systems that permit remote operations; and systems using short range wireless communications
Threat 17	Hosted 3rd party software, e.g. entertainment applications, used as a means to attack vehicle systems
Threat 18	Devices connected to external interfaces e.g. USB ports, OBD port, used as a means to attack vehicle systems

TABLE 6: POTENTIAL TARGETS OF, OR MOTIVES FOR, AN ATTACK

Category: Potential targets of, or motivations for, an attack:

Threat 19	Extraction of vehicle data/code
Threat 20	Manipulation of vehicle data/code
Threat 21	Erasure of data/code
Threat 22	Introduction of malware
Threat 23	Introduction of new software or overwrite of existing software
Threat 24	Disruption of systems or operations
Threat 25	Manipulation of vehicle parameters

TABLE 7: POTENTIAL VULNERABILITIES THAT COULD BE EXPLOITED IF NOT SUFFICIENTLY PROTECTED OR HARDENED

Category: Potential vulnerabilities that could be exploited if not sufficiently protected or hardened:

Threat 26	Cryptographic technologies can be compromised or are insufficiently applied
Threat 27	Component parts or supplies could be compromised to permit vehicles to be attacked
Threat 28	Software or hardware development permits vulnerabilities
Threat 29	Network design introduces vulnerabilities
Threat 30	Physical loss of data can occur
Threat 31	Unintended transfer of data can occur
Threat 32	Physical manipulation of systems can enable an attack

These 32 key cyber threats are important in the design phase of the system as well as for testing. In the design phase, measures need to be implemented in order to avoid this threat from being exploited. In the testing phase, these measures need to be tested systematically.

2.2 Requirements regarding physical testing

2.2.1 Proving ground testing

Proving ground testing (also known as test-track testing) is a valuable tool within the test toolchain for automotive development and has decades of long successful demonstration of its advantages in several vehicle domains (powertrain, brakes, dynamics, etc...) and with a huge potential in the CAD context, particular for testing, validation and certification.

Proving ground testing can have different objectives and it is important to differentiate the purpose of the testing when entering the test tracks (development phases, type approval or consumer testing).

On the one side, one can enter to the test tracks to validate a function/functionality in its development phase. In this case, the requirements of each use case are more related to the description of the use case itself and its functionalities (e.g. detailed ODD, thorough description with the parameters defined, specifications of how the vehicle must behave in front to a situation, etc.). Here, the main goal of entering the test tracks is to check the performance of the function and to test the limits so the main requirements for each use case is to know where the limits are and to identify bugs, errors, etc.

On the other side, one can enter to the test tracks once the vehicle has passed the validation phase and it is in a more mature phase, which is the type approval. Chapter 2.6.2 is focused in the needs and requirements from the type approval point of view. The physical tests that are part of a homologation process are defined by regulations. In this case, all the functionalities that compose a use case will have to pass several tests independently, so the requirements in this case will be imposed by the regulatory framework.

Similarly, when entering the proving ground to perform consumer testing tests, the specifications of the tests are defined from outside (e.g. EuroNCAP). In this case, not only the behaviour of the targets but also the behaviour of the vehicle under test is more strictly defined by the consumer testing association. This could change in the future when vehicles could have more decision capability and thus different actions could be taken to avoid an accident.

Proving ground testing provides several advantages over other test tools, the main one being the possibility of emulating close to real-world conditions with the possibility to test in a parameterized manner. It is also important to highlight the following characteristics:

- **Safety:** Due to the controlled environment a proving ground represents, safety can be assured for the vehicle and the involved humans in the test. It also allows to test safety performance limits of a particular (driving) function without any risk to other road users.
- **Robustness:** Test results are robust due to the control of the parameters of the test case including intrinsic characteristics of the vehicle under test (or ego-vehicle) and extrinsic ones as other vehicles and targets, physical and digital infrastructure and in some cases even weather conditions. This control of parameters and characteristics from the test responsible allows to have flexibility when defining the test cases but also robust results.
- **Repeatability:** As a consequence of robustness, the tests, if the intrinsic and extrinsic variables can be reproduced accurately, can be obtained in different proving grounds or test houses. Repeatability of results is critical to create trust between the associated stakeholders (industry, academia and public authorities) and it's the basis of current type approval regulations and consumer testing protocols.

Although proving ground has clear advantages, they cannot be considered to work isolated of other test instances as simulation and/or field operational tests (FOTs). Simulation allows cost-effective testing of hundreds and even thousands of different scenarios, with continuously expanding flexibility in the different involved parameters. However, current state-of-the-art simulation cannot be compared with real physical testing in a proving ground in terms of realism.

On the contrary, FOTs (see section 2.2.2) are the most realistic test instance, however it is very complex to specify and control the test parameters.

Proving ground testing closes this gap between simulation and FOTs but in general it has some limitations in building complex scenarios. The higher number of variables and the possibility to recreate them in proving ground at a reasonable cost-benefit is of key importance. The final objective is to be able to translate logical scenarios to concrete scenarios and derive final test cases to be executed in an accurate way. Among the variables that are relevant for CAD we may find:

- Physical infrastructure: Availability of representative test tracks for the use case under test. This includes different types of roads or the possibility to adapt them to real world scenarios: horizontal and vertical signage, ramps, types of road pavement, tunnels, bridges, etc... It is also relevant to highlight specific types of physical infrastructure as e.g. parking lots that are very variable by nature.
- Digital infrastructure: Availability of digital resources that are relevant for the performance of the driving function under test. Digital infrastructure has traditionally been considered a commodity for the correct operation of test tracks and the execution of tests but currently they are also the subject of the test itself. Digital infrastructure is critical for the testing of Key Enabling Technologies. Among them you can differentiate subtypes of digital infrastructure:
 - Communications: Availability and possibility to tweak or modify the connectivity between the ego-vehicle, the infrastructure as well as other vehicles or targets involved in the tests. Different access technologies are currently considered as the most promising ones for CAD: ETSI ITS G5 (DSRC in the US) and cellular technologies (4G/LTE and 5G). Cellular technologies, in their latest releases from 3GPP now include V2V capabilities (LTE-V2X and C-V2X). For the particular case of GNSS positioning, beyond communications with the geo-stationary satellites, it is important the communication with external services that improve localisation (e.g. EGNOS, D-GPS messages, etc...).
 - Digital assets: They support the CAD driving functions in several ways e.g. positioning and navigation. Among them it is important to highlight high definition maps that enable advanced navigation of vehicles. Usually, these digital assets shall be communicated (bidirectionally) to and from the ego-vehicle making use of cloud-based services and/or edge computing servers.
 - Cybersecurity: Once communication is enabled in a vehicle, cybersecurity requirements grow exponentially from the baseline of isolated vehicles and consequently need to be addressed as a requirement as well as a test objective including the whole data chain.
- Targets and additional road users: Some concrete scenarios may require a large number of external objects involved in the test. These external objects may be of different nature: other vehicles, vulnerable road users as pedestrians or cyclist, random obstacles. Depending of the use case under test the relation and/or interaction of the object can also vary (e.g. a truck in a steady state platoon in respect to the other trucks in the platoon). Sometimes these objects can be real in a test-track test (e.g. another vehicle or truck), however for safety, these objects need to be substituted by targets that emulate the shape, reflectivity or movements of the real object they are representing. In any of these cases, the inclusion of a large number of objects increases the complexity of the test execution due to the technical complexity of coordinating all the objects.

2.2.2 Field operational tests

Field operational tests (FOTs) as large-scale testing procedures, with the aim to assess the quality and robustness of automated driving functions, have different high-level requirements to be performed pragmatically and at the same time to guarantee a high level of scientific quality. Functions should be tested under normal operating conditions in a function typical environment using different quasi-experimental methods. The functional behaviour needs to be compared to a baseline condition. This baseline condition needs to be described prior to the test and should define at least the level of baseline assistance or automation (SAE L0, L1 or L2), to standardize expected driving behaviour and performance in certain situations.

Furthermore, test conditions (road type, infrastructure, traffic, weather, etc.) should be standardized as far as possible to allow comparison between different vehicles, test procedures or test labs. Also, the impact of driver behavior (driver override, take-over) should be recorded/reported as well as the behavior of other road users (other drivers, pedestrians, etc.), since driver vehicle interaction as well as interaction with other road users will have a significant influence on the test results. How to take this influence into account should be discussed and standardized prior to the performance of the test.

2.3 Requirements regarding model-based testing

A well-established design paradigm from robotics and automation literature is the *Sense-Plan-Act* structure, which can be seen in Figure 7. In this model, Sensing & Perception (including Localization), Planning & Control and Actuation & Stability provide a general, implementation-independent, view of the automated vehicle system.

Based on [10] the capabilities of this basic *Sense-Plan-Act* functions are:

- Sense:
 - Perceive relevant static and dynamic objects in proximity to the automated vehicle
 - Determine its location
 - Predict the future of relevant actors
- Plan:
 - Create a collision-free and lawful driving plan
- Act:
 - Correctly execute and actuate the driving plan
 - Communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users

FIGURE 7: SENSE-PLAN-ACT DESIGN PARADIGM [1]

Model-based testing can help to understand the possible behaviours and outcomes of a system in a virtual setting that can be directly controlled and has much higher efficiency compared to real world testing. Furthermore, tests that include safety critical settings may not be feasible for real world testing (either on proving ground (PG) or public road tests) and are only possible with a virtual environment. For automotive automated applications, model-based testing considers either an entire system (e.g. a full vehicle with CAD function), a subsystem (e.g. an actuator or a hardware controller) or a component (e.g. a sensor or a communication bus). [10]

Model-based testing introduces the appropriate models to represent the behaviour of the system of interest in the necessary degree of detail. Models are always abstractions from the physical reality and rely heavily on simplifications of the true complexity in the real world. As consequence of that, simulations for model-based testing can only be accurate to a certain degree. The desired level of accuracy required for a simulation model depends on the test goal and needs to be verified and validated separately.

To obtain needed requirements for model-based testing, first a top level overview of the general structure used for simulations of CAD systems needs to be established. This top level approach can be seen in Figure 8. This approach can be seen as an appropriate modification of the classic *Sense-Plan-Act* – structure for model-based testing purposes, as the *Sense-Plan-Act* – structure is based in the *Driving Function*, adding the necessary blocks (*Sensors* and *Vehicle Dynamics*) for interaction with the environment. Every logical block is either virtual or real, depending on the test platform and test strategy [10], as explained later on.

The blocks have the following meaning:

- **Driving Function:**
 - It is the main part of this top level approach framework. Implemented in an autonomous vehicle it is acting as the decision-maker of the whole system based on sensor input. The input from the *Sensors* block includes every sensor available to the system (e.g. LiDAR, Camera, GPS, IMU, ...). In which format the input is delivered highly depends on the sensor type and driving function. This can range from raw data to processed object-level data. If the driving function has decided on certain actions, based on the sensory input, the appropriate actions are transferred to the *Vehicle Dynamics* block.
- **Vehicle Dynamics:**
 - This block contains either the physical or virtual representation of the vehicle under test (VUT), equipped with the driving function. It takes the input from the driving function (driving commands like gas and brake pedal angle) and acts accordingly. In case of a virtual model it is part of the virtual environment and underlies the respective physics engine.
- **Sensors:**
 - This block gets all its input from the respective virtual environment. The model accuracy highly depends on the needed quality of sensor data, which then also reflects on the modelling approach for the virtual environment. In general, for the typical, in autonomous systems used sensors, there are three types of modelling techniques, distinguished by abstraction level (based on [11]):
 - **Ideal sensor models:**
 - These models are generating object lists, which are based on perfect data from the virtual environment regarding objects like cars and vulnerable road users (VRU) in the sensors field of view. The models are simple enough to be easily used in real-time simulation environments and can also be used as ground-truth data.
 - **Probabilistic sensor models:**
 - Based on ideal models, these types of models are adding statistical failure rates. Object list entries can be modified, or a certain level of noise can be added (depending on the kind of data).
 - **Physical sensor models:**
 - These kinds of models are based on the actual physical principles of the respective sensor type, hence the name. Thus, every type of sensor needs a different physical sensor model. The models are usually very calculation heavy and most of the time not suitable for real-time simulations. Most of the time they are used for the design of the actual sensor (in reality). These types of sensors also hold the most requirements to the virtual environment, as the physical principles must be able to correctly be depicted in the virtual world, which is a challenge in itself.
- **Virtual Environment (including Scenario Modelling):**
 - The virtual environment is where everything comes together and is represented in order to simulate the real world. Basically, it can be split in two different categories:
 - **Static Environment:**
 - In this category falls everything which does not change its location during scenario simulation. This includes objects like houses and of course the whole road network, which is defined with the official standard OpenDRIVE [12].
 - **Dynamic Environment:**
 - Contrary to the static environment, the dynamic environment contains everything which changes its location during the scenario simulation. This includes mostly traffic objects like cars and VRUs.

In this block also the scenario modelling (applicable for scenario-based testing) can be placed in, as it defines how certain actors in the virtual environment move and or react, as well as the road network on which the scenario is based upon in the OpenDRIVE standard. The scenario can be described with the official standard OpenSCENARIO [13], which is able to describe the actions of all actors in the virtual environment, which are participants of the scenario.

Different simulators exist for creating the necessary virtual environment, which all have advantages and disadvantages, depending on the use case. In general, every simulator consists of a graphic (for realistic 3D rendering) and physics engine (for realistic movements) for modelling the respective behaviours [14].

FIGURE 8: TOP LEVEL APPROACH FOR MODEL-BASED TESTING

The just described framework works as basis for different model-based testing approaches. All these approaches have one thing in common: At least one element of Figure 8 is virtual, leading to the conclusion that additional considerations for the verification of the used simulation models need to be made. In case of testing CAD functions, a correlation between simulation and proving ground results in a certain basic scenario is necessary in order to execute further simulation and produce meaningful results, which help to validate the driving function of the VUT.

In a practical sense this means the following for every block of Figure 8:

- **Driving Function:**
 - In order to be able to test and therefore verify PG with simulation results, the driving function needs to be defined in a correct way, including the respective operational design domain (ODD). The ODD defines the environment conditions under which the driving function can operate in a safe way. In addition to that a functional description of the driving function itself is necessary to understand the purpose of the function. This should include failure mode behaviour, the aforementioned ODD (including ODD elements) and the tactical manoeuvre behaviour (e.g. perform lane change/ low-speed merge) as well as the object and event detection and response (OEDR). OEDR represents the ability of the CAD function to detect any circumstance that is immediately relevant to the driving task and implement an appropriate response [6]
- **Vehicle Dynamics:**
 - Validating the vehicle dynamics model of the simulation highly depends on the use case, which reflects the needed model accuracy (in terms of longitudinal and lateral motion). As stated in [7], in general, the passive vehicle (without active ESC controller) model must be validated at first for steady-state circular driving according to ISO 19364 [8], before the influence of the ESC controller can be added for Sine-with-Dwell tests in ISO 19365 [9]. If possible, values for lateral and longitudinal acceleration, steering wheel angle, pedal positions, sideslip angle and roll angle

as well as the current position (measured with differential GPS for desired accuracy) should be obtained.

- Other parameters like vehicle mass and centre of gravity can be determined by static measurements according to ISO 10392 [10] and are an absolute necessity for conducting model-based testing. Other possible necessary requirements are highly depended on the actual manoeuvres executed by the CAD function in the chosen use case.
- **Sensors:**
 - For the sensors, as minimal requirements needed for the ideal sensor models, the field of view of every sensor, which is needed for the driving function, needs to be known. In addition to that, the actual sensor positions on the VUT must be known. If more sophisticated sensor models are needed, more information is required. For probabilistic sensor models, this includes the knowledge of statistical failure rates and for physical models this includes detailed knowledge of the respective sensor properties.
 - For verification of the used sensor models in simulation, feedback from the VUT in real world tests (e.g. on PG), at least in form of object lists from the respective sensors, would be needed.
- **Virtual Environment (including Scenario Modeling):**
 - To model the virtual environment a minimal knowledge of the PG, on which the testing is carried out, is needed. This includes most importantly the road network (defined in OpenDRIVE).
 - The scenario description itself (defined in OpenSCENARIO) should be the same in the virtual environment as well as on the PG.

HEADSTART will deliver results to the three defined main pillars (target groups):

- *Testing and validation: Technology developers*
- *Assessment: Consumer testing associations*
- *Certification: Type approval authorities*

Each of those three target groups have partly different objectives when it comes to testing CAD functions and therefore the simulation activities greatly differ between these groups. One of many reasons for that is the difference in access to the various systems and data from the VUT, especially regarding the CAD function. While usually the technology developers have the most access (referred to as white box-access for total access and grey box for partial access), it decreases for the assessment associations and certification authorities (up to no access, which is referred to as black box).

Due to this reason, especially for technology development, different types of model-based testing possibilities have emerged, differing in the testing goal, as well as the development stage. As stated in [10], [15] and [16], mainly three different groups of model-based testing approaches exist (see Figure 9):

- **Model in the Loop (MiL) & Software in the Loop (SiL):**
 - SiL simulation can be viewed as the traditional simulation system, where a subset (MiL) or all underlying software required for the CAD function is modelled [15]. It can be used to verify the code of the CAD function, where hardware components, sensors and vehicle dynamics are simulated [11].
- **Hardware in the Loop (HiL):**
 - In general HiL simulators can be used to validate real hardware in an early development phase, without the need of a prototype vehicle, as any missing vehicle components can be simulated [16]. This hardware can be on component level (e.g. sensors) or subsystem level (e.g. system without sensors, controller, CAD function) [15]. HiL can be used to test the real code of the CAD function on the target hardware (electronic control unit, ECU), leaving the rest as virtual elements in the real-time simulation.
- **Vehicle in the Loop (ViL or VHiL):**

- ViL simulation allows for a more integrated test and analysis by leveraging the VUT including the subsystems. The VUT could be placed on a roller test bench, such as a chassis-dynamometer, to allow physical actuation of the steering, throttle and brake systems to get the wheels rolling and turning, while the vehicle remains in place. The simulation system could be tied into both the roller bench and the vehicle itself. The interface with the vehicle could allow for injection of sensor data to simulate terrain and objects [15].

The three described possibilities can be seen in Figure 9 as well, where the blocks *Vehicle* refer to the *Vehicle dynamics (or general the VUT)* of Figure 8 and the *Function* refers to the *driving function (CAD function)* of Figure 8. To be able to compare the different approaches with a real drive, the same starting point (the same scenario) needs to be defined. Afterwards the deviations are evaluated, with the SiL/MiL approach having only virtual elements, the HiL having the CAD function as real element and the ViL simulation having the VUT (including the CAD function) as real element.

FIGURE 9: DIFFERENT MODEL-BASED TESTING APPROACHES AND POSSIBLE COMPARISON WITH REAL DRIVE [7]

In Table 8 all the gathered requirements for model-based testing are listed. It includes necessary information from the CAD function (implemented in the VUT) as well as the requirements for the logical block (see Figure 8.) sensors, vehicle dynamics and virtual environment.

TABLE 8: REQUIREMENTS ON THE USE CASE FOR THE MODEL-BASED TESTING

CAD function
Tactical maneuvers
ODD elements
OEDR
Failure Modes
CAD function as code (for SiL/MiL) and on target HW (ECU) (for HiL)
Sensors
Sensor setup (field of view from all the sensors + sensor position on VUT)
Object-list based feedback from the driven scenarios of the VUT
GPS data from VUT during scenario (for KET positioning)
For probabilistic sensor models: statistical failure rates
For physical sensor models: detailed knowledge of the respective sensor properties
Vehicle Dynamics
Mass / dimensions / Center of gravity/ (Moment of inertia for z-axis) of VUT
Minimal vehicle dynamics measurements: Exact position (with D-GPS) and orientation
Vehicle dynamics measurements from scenarios (and/or basic scenarios) including lateral & longitudinal acceleration, steering wheel angle, pedal positions
VUT on test bench (for ViL)
Virtual Environment – Static
OpenDRIVE description for the scenario (including potential special conditions on PG)
Virtual Environment – Dynamic
OpenSCENARIO description (of the scenario to be tested on PG and for virtual testing)

2.4 Definition and availability of scenarios

The HEADSTART project utilizes a scenario-based approach for the efficient testing of automated driving functions. Thus, to define use cases within HEADSTART it is necessary to have scenarios for testing available. Scenarios are extracted from real-world data, e.g. FOT or naturalistic driving studies (NDSs), and saved in a database. There are several projects which consider this approach and have scenarios available like the German PEGASUS or the French MOOVE project. This results in three prerequisites for the definition of use cases within the HEADSTART project.

There needs to be recorded scenarios available from a database meeting the requirements regarding especially the ODD but also in terms of other constraints of the abstract scenario definition.

There needs to be a scenario concept which is aligned with the overall methodology and which supports especially the required ODD.

The scenario concept and the available scenarios need to cover all the required layers (1-6) which have an impact on the use case and therefore need to be regarded when it comes to testing.

By analysing on the one hand projects in which partners of the HEADSTART consortium are involved, like PEGASUS or MOOVE, and on the other hand projects with publicly available scenario concepts and scenarios, the availability of scenarios for the definition of use cases is described in the following.

The German project PEGASUS utilizes a data-driven approach to extract scenarios for the verification and validation of automated driving functions. The project is focused on highways, thus the scenario concept is well defined for highways, as well as the field data, making it an optimal source for driving functions which are operated on highways. However, especially passenger cars are regarded, but all other sorts of traffic is available to be tested as well. The PEGASUS database can be accessed by ika and should be utilized for use cases on highways. Restrictions apply only if demands on KETs cannot be combined with the utilized challenger-scenario approach of PEGASUS.

The French MOOVE project has several types of scenarios available, reaching from highway to some urban areas especially for personal cars. However, there are no scenarios for valet parking or urban shuttles available. Most scenarios are available for the highway. The project's scenarios can be accessed through VEDECOM, being a partner of the HEADSTART consortium.

2.5 Requirements on collaboration partners

Many CAD-related projects have already been identified to potentially provide input to HEADSTART, either on use case level, specific functions/tools they use, or in the pilot phase they will be or are implementing. This collaboration entails parameters and implications that need to be clarified.

- **Data ownership:** The main issue among collaboration is the fact that existing HEADSTART partners already participate in other consortia/initiatives and should first explore whether not public data or deliverables of that project could be used for the scope of HEADSTART. Each case is different, so a generic approach should be followed and applied accordingly. Eventually, the project should be able to receive from the targeted project/consortium both a written consensus to officially offer valuable information and the data/datasets/tools etc. themselves for free or restricted use from HEADSTART.
- **Timing:** This parameter should be taken into consideration, because the ending of a project could amend the interest, the actual cooperation and the terms of support that could be provided. Specifically, since HEADSTART will be based on actual pilot use cases, it should be clear when and for how long use cases could support the project.
- **Collaboration framework:** Bilateral discussions with other initiatives and projects should conclude to official arrangements between the involved projects. Both consortia should support each other and act on the agreed plan. This framework should briefly and clearly highlight the responsible owners, their obligations and rights, the terms for using data/datasets/tools/etc., the timeframe conditions for both the project's running duration and the period after its end.

2.6 Relevance to key user groups

2.6.1 OEMs, Tier1s

Use cases should be evaluated by testing the test object in simulation, driving simulators, test track and open road.

Testing by simulation (MiL and SiL) is expected to be used for standard test cases but should also be used for extreme cases difficult to perform in real world. The simulation environment should involve a large number of scenarios with a lot of variations, such as perturbations of the scenes. Simulation should also be possible to use for evaluating driving policies.

Testing in driving simulators should be possible to perform to test user experience, human machine interface validation, take-over requests, etc.

Testing at test track (proving ground) should be possible to do in a repeatable way. This type of testing should be done to assess performance and sensor verification. Test track testing is expected to be done in a controlled environment, with the possibility to test with real environment and sensors, and with the possibility to get feedback from the driver's feelings. To maximize the number of test cases to be tested, preparation time should therefore be minimized. The number of scenarios should be kept as small as possible. Some environmental conditions such as rain, temperature, snow or nighttime can be limitations. This is expected to be a problem for Highway Chauffeur / Pilot (SAE level 3 & 4) dependent on the sensor solutions.

Test at open road (real-world testing) is the only place where there is a real environment, a real system and a real-world high level of variability. Open road is used for the final verification to control that the system works under certain parameters. In the open road testing, it should be possible to perform sensor verification, acceptance of other road users, customer performance synthesis on real traffic and to detect unforeseeable scenarios. The inconvenient part is that the open road testing is time consuming, not repeatable, and there is no control over the environment (tests are done under different weather/traffic conditions). Some possible requirements for the infrastructure of test facilities could be: Connectivity, Electric Vehicles (EV) chargers, potholes cancellation, lane markings with reflective paintings, High Definition (HD) Map with regular updates. In France, the roads need to be compliant with the French road guideline T80 (i.e. dual carriage motorway with physical barrier, limited access, separated from the environment, no intersection).

It is of high importance that the technical documentation provided by the type approval authorities is well described. The limits of the operational domain of the function must be accurate so it is easy to identify the most relevant cases to perform. Since it is in practice impossible to test the whole space of thinkable scenarios that will be met in the real world, scenarios should be selected according to performance indicators.

The trend where the responsibility of the driving task is shifted from the end-user to the OEM increases the need for defining reliable test methods. In addition, without any legal framework i.e. type approval leaves the OEMs unprotected against the risks of implementing CAD technologies on the roads. Finally, OEMs, Tier1s, as well as other development stakeholders, require cost-time effective and robust methods and tools for the testing and validation of CAD vehicles.

2.6.2 Type approval authorities

Key user groups have different requirements in performing tests and assessments of automated driving functions. One relevant group in this respect are type-approval authorities. Here, it is important that the technical documentation provided by the OEM is well described. The limits of the operational domain of the function must be accurate so that it is easy to identify the most relevant cases or worst test cases to test. In some cases, if a specific test cannot be practically achieved due to e.g. the limitations of the test facilities, with the consent of the type approval authority be fulfilled through the use of documentation. For this reason, the documentation provided must be complete and accurate.

The test track of the proving ground must be easy to adapt. (e.g. different lane geometries). According to the test requirements of the most advanced functionalities that can be (type) approved nowadays, the test conditions and the vehicle test speed shall be within the operating range of the system. This means that you may need to adapt the test track or the testing area to the system that you are evaluating. Also, the new layout of the lanes used in the testing must be reported with the test results. Furthermore, technical service and OEM must go together during the development phase, to ensure the fulfilment of the functional safety requirements (e.g. SOTIF, ISO 26262, etc.).

In addition, test tools (synchronized and repeatable testing with multiple vehicle targets, other road users (e.g. VRU)) must be robust and available on proving grounds. Because of geo-fencing (required by type approval), it is important to ensure that all kinds of intended system functionalities are available and testable on proving grounds.

2.6.3 Consumer Testing

Consumer testing defines scenarios that represent, in a simplified way, important real-life accident scenarios that could result in injured or killed car occupants or other road users. The key parameters to evaluate the relevance of a scenario are the following:

- **Injury risk functions:** The injury risk function is the average relationship between risk of injury and the speed difference based on a particular sample of casualties and accidents. The AIS (**Abbreviated Injury Scale**) is a 0-6 numeric scale with 0 being no injury and 6 being un-survivable injury. Usually Euro NCAP focuses on injuries having an AIS 3 or higher including fatalities.
- **Crash frequency** (i.e., accident distribution over impact speed): Beside the injury risk at certain impact speeds or velocity differences, the importance of speed ranges depends on the frequency of accidents occurring at these speeds.

The expected number of injured occupants for a certain scenario is computed as a weighted sum of the number of crashes at different velocity changes with weights given by the injury risk curve. The scenarios to be tested are the one with the largest number of injured people considering also that the systems on the market will need to be able to cover the scenario.

From the use case point of view the biggest requirement imposed by consumer testing association is that the function provides some safety benefit. This means that the more interesting use cases are the ones for which the number of accidents and injuries is high but could decrease thanks to the use of automated/autonomous driving functions.

3 Use cases: Definitions and availability

This chapter describes the use cases that are candidates to be selected for further use in HEADSTART. Following the results of the surveys and interviews with stakeholders and user groups reported in D1.2, the use cases investigated are

1. Truck Platooning
2. Highway Pilot
3. Traffic Jam Chauffeur
4. Valet Parking
5. Urban Automated Shuttle.

3.1 Truck Platooning

3.1.1 Description

In partial driving automation (L2) truck platooning, the vehicles travel with small inter-vehicle distances, enabled by information sharing through V2V communication, at up to highway speeds. Among the advantages are improved aerodynamic effectiveness and performance, and a resulting reduction of fuel consumption, as well as a steadier traffic flow. The driver of the lead vehicle conducts the platoon, running in either automated or manual mode, and the following vehicles run in automated mode.

FIGURE 10: LAYERED PLATOONING STRUCTURE.

The vehicles should be able to keep their position in the platoon with a safe distance to their neighbours and manage disturbances introduced by other road users (e.g. through cut-ins). The state and driving behaviour of each vehicle is transmitted by V2V communication to the vehicle behind it, including descriptions of vehicle characteristics, such as braking capacity and load. The platooning function also handles management aspects such as forming, merging and dissolving platoons as well as the interaction with other road users and road infrastructure requirements.

The platooning function is typically comprised of layers, responsible for decisions on different timescales. The operational layer contains the safety critical functionality, e.g. distance keeping and assurance existence of fail-safe manoeuvres. Longitudinal control is coordinated and utilizes information exchange over V2V, while lateral control is a stand-alone, vehicle specific component. The tactical layer contains functionality for manoeuvring, such as platoon-merging and the control of platoon wide parameters such as target speed and target gaps. Strategic and service layers contain higher level functionality, such as platoon formation scheduling (which vehicle joins which platoon), traffic flow control, logistics operations and fleet management.

Area of application

TABLE 9: AREA OF APPLICATION - TRUCK PLATOONING

Entry	Value	Comment
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic	
Road Type	Highway or comparable	
Admissible Road Infrastructure	Roads, tunnels, vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses	
Dedicated infrastructure	High level functionality (strategic and services layers) requires connected infrastructure. Basic level functionality (tactical and operational layers) rely on V2V short range connectivity	
Traffic Density	Variable, heavy traffic and its interaction with the platoon must be considered	

Entry	Value	Comment
Speed Range	0-90 km/h	Depending of applicable traffic rules
Environmental Conditions	Non-extreme weather conditions	
Vehicle Configuration	Mass 12 to 44 t.	

Reliance of KETs identified in HEADSTART

TABLE 10: RELIANCE OF KETS IDENTIFIED IN HEADSTART – TRUCK PLATOONING

KET	Function's usage
Communication	<p>Vehicle-to-vehicle communication used in the operational layer (for e.g. inter vehicle distance regulation), in the tactical layer (for e.g. setting and adjusting inter-vehicle gaps). In the higher layers: for the strategic layer (coordination between platoons and/or potential platooning candidates) and the service layer (overall coordination of trucks and truck platoons with added value services e.g. logistic operator). See Ensemble project deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4: Functional specification for white-label truck (Operational & Tactical layers) • D2.6: V1 Functional specification for intelligent infrastructure (Strategic/Services layers) • D2.8: Platooning protocol definition and Communication strategy
Positioning	<p>In-lane positioning used in the operational layer for lateral control, relative inter-vehicle positioning in operational layer for distance keeping and longitudinal control, absolute positioning (through GNSS and high-definition maps) used in the tactical layer for e.g. deciding gaps and speeds due to environmental and zone conditions.</p> <p>Non mission-critical positioning requirements for the higher layers (strategic and service).</p> <p>See Ensemble project deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.4: Functional specification for white-label truck (Operational & Tactical layers) • D2.6: V1 Functional specification for intelligent infrastructure (Strategic/Services layers) • D2.8: Platooning protocol definition and Communication strategy

KET	Function's usage
Cybersecurity	<p>Security techniques are implemented to ensure the correctness of the identity of the platoon members. Other security techniques are used to establish the correctness of the information exchanged between partners. Confidentiality measures may be taken to reduce the risk of external partners trying to read and send false messages.</p> <p>See Ensemble project deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D2.8: Platooning protocol definition and Communication strategy • D2.9: Security framework of platooning

3.1.2 Representative scenario

A non-platooning vehicle cuts in to the platoon necessitating an adaptation of the velocities and gaps between platoon members to ensure safety. Platoon members will - based on the cut-in - adapt their velocity and gap towards the cut-in vehicle and between the platoon members to assure safety. In principle the platoon will remain as one entity (V2V link up) with an intruder till some exit conditions may apply that cause the platoon to split up.

Initial condition

A group of two or more automated cooperative vehicles are in line with aligned speeds, maintaining a close distance using wireless communication. All vehicles are within the ODD of the platooning function. For each vehicle but the first (the leader) the forward vehicle is within sensor view. All vehicles are within communication range with at least its forward and rearward vehicles when such are present (only forward and rearward for the platoon's leading and trailing vehicle respectively). Control messages are sent and received according to specification.

A non-cooperative vehicle with the same velocity as the platoon plans to cut in to the platoon.

Sequence of scenes

TABLE 11: INITIAL CONDITION AND SEQUENCE OF SCENES - TRUCK PLATOONING

#	Description	Illustration
1	Initial condition, the cutting in vehicle is detected.	
2	Cut in completed	
3	The vehicle behind the intruding vehicle slows down to increase distance.	

#	Description	Illustration
4	The intruding vehicle slows down to expand gap to its forward vehicle	

Terminal condition

As initial condition, but with an intruding vehicle between two of the platooning vehicles, blocking the rearward vehicle's sensor view of the preceding vehicle in the platoon and prompting a larger gap.

Functional Requirements

TABLE 12: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS - TRUCK PLATOONING

Functional Requirements	Source
The platoon system in the ego vehicle shall broadcast its actual and intended acceleration via V2V to enable following vehicles to detect emergency braking events	Ensemble D2.4
The platoon system in the ego vehicle shall broadcast a cut-in when detected.	Ensemble D2.4
The platoon system in the ego vehicle shall receive platooning information via V2V needed to maintain the platooning time gap, for platoon cohesion and for platoon standby from vehicles in the platoon.	Ensemble D2.4
The platoon system in the ego vehicle shall broadcast the platooning information via V2V, which is needed by the other platoon members' control system	Ensemble D2.4
The system shall keep a time gap to the preceding vehicle such that it can avoid collision if the preceding vehicle is braking to standstill with its maximum deceleration capacity.	Ensemble D2.4
The system shall communicate the ego vehicle maximum brake deceleration capacity on dry asphalt to the following vehicle.	Ensemble D2.4
The system shall never keep a closer time gap than 0.8 s to the preceding vehicle in the platoon. Time gap is here defined as the distance to the preceding vehicle divided by the ego vehicle speed	Ensemble D2.4
During steady-state platooning, the system shall keep the selected time gap without amplifying disturbances (e.g. velocity variations) in the platoon, also known as string stability.	Ensemble D2.4
The system shall not brake more than needed to keep the selected time gap to the preceding vehicle.	Ensemble D2.4

Functional Requirements	Source
The system shall not brake with a deceleration that is higher (stronger braking) than the maximum brake deceleration capacity communicated to the other platoon vehicles.	Ensemble D2.4
During platooning the vehicle shall detect cut in vehicles as these intrude in the direct path (width of path = vehicle width) of the ego vehicle at a minimum distance of 1m.	Ensemble D2.4
During all phases of platooning the platoon system vehicle shall measure the velocity of vehicles in the field of view with an accuracy of 0.4km/h with a range of +300...- 90km/h	Ensemble D2.4
A platooning vehicle shall detect the preceding vehicle and measure the position of this with a longitudinal accuracy of 0.4m	Ensemble D2.4

3.1.3 Examples of abstract scenarios

TABLE 13: LIST OF SCENARIOS – TRUCK PLATOONING – CUT-IN SUB-USE CASE

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Cut-through	As “Cut-in”, but the intruding vehicle cuts out of the platoon, prompting additional change of gaps and velocities.	ENSEMBLE D2.4
Join from behind	A Platoon Candidate sends a request to join a forward target (single vehicle or existing platoon), which performs adaptation of gap and velocities as response.	ENSEMBLE D2.4
Follow to stop	The platoon leader reduces its speed, and following vehicles adjust their velocity accordingly. When speed is below threshold and stationary, longitudinal control in follower is handed to driver, who must intervene to resume platoon operation.	ENSEMBLE D2.4
Platoon gap adaptation due to I2V interaction	I2V communication informs all vehicles in the platoon of a zone policy stating changed gaps/speed/lateral position for a specific zone defined. The platoon coordinates to apply the zone policy to the platoon configuration.	ENSEMBLE D2.4

3.1.4 Related projects and initiatives

TABLE 14: RELATED PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES – TRUCK PLATOONING

ENSEMBLE

Period	June 2018 – May 2021
Context/Funding	European project (H2020)
HEADSTART KETs	Cybersecurity, Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	TNO, VOLVO Group, ERTICO, IDIADA, IVECO
Description	<p>The main goal of the ENSEMBLE project is to pave the way for the adoption of multi-brand truck platooning in Europe to improve fuel economy, traffic safety and throughput. This will be demonstrated by driving seven differently branded trucks in one (or more) platoon(s) under real world traffic conditions across national borders.</p> <p>Following objectives are defined:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interoperable platooning — when forming a scalable, multi-brand convoy – the vehicles must be compatible to ensure correct and safe operation on public roads. • Safe Platooning — in ENSEMBLE designing fail-safe and fault tolerant mechanisms is a priority to include safe interaction both within the platoon and with other road users using secure wireless communication. • Real-life platooning — Practical tests on closed testing grounds and in real life serve to an experience of ‘learning by doing’, to assess the impact on traffic and infrastructure and to promote multi-brand platooning through a presentation of a multi-brand platoon in real traffic conditions across national borders. • Embedded platooning — ENSEMBLE will design an interface to cloud-based services so that the platooning concept can be seamlessly integrated into the logistic value chain.
Link	https://platooningensemble.eu/

3.2 Highway Pilot

3.2.1 Description

The highway pilot use case can be defined as the Conditional (L3) or Highly Automated Driving (L4) in non-congested conditions, on highways and other structurally separated roads, with a speed range of 30 km/h to 130 km/h (180 km/h in some special conditions e.g. German Autobahn).

It allows the driver to turn attention away from the driving task for a longer period. The vehicle handles all of the driving-related tasks like overtaking slower vehicles, driving in tunnels or through toll gates. In addition, the system initiates the process of returning responsibility back to the driver. In emergency situations the functions execute defined actions:

- At L3: In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserve to orientate himself and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop. If possible, depending on the traffic situation and system capabilities, the reduced risk conditions will include the necessary lane changes to stop at the hard shoulder e.g. emergency lane or side of the road.
- At L4: There is no request from the system to the driver to take over when the system is in normal operation area (i.e. on the motorway), so sleeping is allowed. In case a situation occurs, when average human driver would try to end the journey or simply stop at the motorway (e.g. extreme weather) and the driver does not take over, the system has the capability to leave the motorway and park the vehicle safely¹.

The main benefits of this use case for the consumers are the added comfort while driving as well as the possibility to focus on something else than the driving task. For the OEMs, this use case is easier to implement than other use cases (e.g. urban driving) because the scenarios encountered are easier to deal with, even at high speed.

¹ Description from ERTRAC roadmap <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

Area of application

TABLE 15: AREA OF APPLICATION – HIGHWAY PILOT

Entry	Value	Comment
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic	
Road Type	Highway or other structurally separated roads Other characteristics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No traffic in the opposite direction on the road (structurally separated roads) limited access: strictly motorized vehicles and trucks (No pedestrian or cyclist) With or without toll gate No intersections and no traffic lights (except some tunnels or bridges). 	
Admissible Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Roads, tunnels, vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses No work zone 	
Dedicated infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear lane markings (e.g. with reflective paint) and visible road signs are needed No connectivity V2I needed but possible (e.g. toll gate or work zone warning) Potholes cancellation HD MAP with regular updates (future development) 	
Traffic Density	Highway pilot = Fluid traffic	
Speed Range	From 30 km/h to 180 km/h	
Environmental Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Min visibility of X, → no fog, no snow (no use of fog lamp) Min friction coef. of Y → no heavy rain and snow The vehicle cannot drive under extreme weather condition (heavy rain, snow, fog ...) The function can work both in day and night time 	
Vehicle Configuration	Passenger cars with a maximum gross vehicle mass up to 3 500 kg Truck with a mass of 12 to 44 t.	

Reliance of KETs identified in HEADSTART

TABLE 16: RELIANCE OF KETs IDENTIFIED IN HEADSTART - HIGHWAY PILOT

KET	Function's usage
Communication	Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication is not necessary for this use case. An example of an application of communicationV2X for this use case could be a vehicle in front of the closest in path vehicle sending a signal to warn other road users that it is breaking.
Positioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-lane positioning used for lateral control, • Relative inter-vehicle positioning for distance keeping with other road users and longitudinal control, • Absolute positioning (through GNSS and Maps) e.g. for deciding gaps and speeds due to environmental and zone conditions
Cybersecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sensors detecting obstacles on the road must be verified and identified by the system supervisor. At least two different types of sensors should be used and controlling each other. • V2I communication (toll gate & work zone) should be secured by the infrastructure owner (e.g. Vinci, APPR ...) • The system supervisor's architecture must be secured (redundancy, control ...) • Over the air download and map cloud must be secured as well.

3.2.2 Representative scenario - "Cut in Front" [Adapted from MOOVE]

A vehicle from an adjacent lane, moves to the ego vehicle lane, and becomes the closest vehicle in the lane in front of the ego.

This functional scenario corresponds to:

The real-life situation where the ego-vehicle is following its trajectory in lane (does not change lane)

Events and actions, where a vehicle located on the adjacent lane (on the right or on the left) of the ego-vehicle is positioning itself on the ego-vehicle lane (in front of the ego).

Initial condition

A vehicle in the adjacent lane of the ego-vehicle intents to merge into the lane of the ego vehicle (Step 1)

Sequence of scenes

TABLE 17: SEQUENCE OF SCENES - HIGHWAY PILOT

#	Description	Illustration
1	Start of the overlap, one of the wheels of the vehicle rolls on the marking of the lane of the ego-vehicle	<p>Cut in front:</p>
2	The vehicle is mostly in the ego-vehicle lane: its centre is in the ego lane The ego vehicle slows down or brakes	
3	The centre of the vehicle returns completely in the trajectory of the ego-vehicle: its centre is in the ego path.	

Terminal condition

The other vehicle has completely entered the ego lane (step 3) and the ego vehicle adapt its speed to the new target vehicle.

Functional Requirements

TABLE 18: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS - HIGHWAY PILOT

Functional Requirements	Source
<p>Determine location: The system should be able to determine its location in relation to the ODD. The vehicle should be able to decide if it is inside or outside of a location-specific ODD. The location in the ODD may be required, depending on the item definition.</p>	Safety first for automated driving [9]
<p>Perceive relevant static and dynamic objects in proximity to the automated vehicle: All entities that an automated driving system requires for its functional behavior should be perceived. The highest priority is placed on entities with an associated risk of collision. Sample entities include dynamic objects (e.g. (vulnerable) road users and characteristics of the respective movement), static instances (e.g. road boundaries, traffic guidance and communication signals) and obstacles.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Predict the future behaviour of relevant objects in order to create a forecast of the environment. The intention of the relevant objects should be interpreted in order to form the basis for predicting future motion.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Create a collision-free and lawful driving plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain a safe lateral and longitudinal distance to other objects. • Comply with all applicable traffic rules within the ODD. • Consider potential areas where objects may be occluded. • In unclear situations the right of way is given, not taken. • If a crash can be avoided without endangering third parties, traffic rules may be prioritized if necessary. 	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Correctly execute the driving plan: The corresponding actuation signals for lateral and longitudinal control should be generated based on the driving plan.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users Automated driving vehicles are required to communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users, depending on the ODD and the use cases</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Determine if specified nominal performance is not achieved: Any element of the automated driving system can, either on its own or in combination with others, result in adverse behaviour. Therefore, mechanisms are required to detect the adverse nominal performance of the system. Typical aspects for influencing the nominal performance are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unwanted human factors, including misuse and manipulations • Deviation of the intended functionality • Technological limitations • Environmental conditions • Systematic and random failure modes 	Safety first for automated driving
<p>In case of failure or at the limit of performance, the system should be able to reach a degraded mode or shelter mode. Define for each failure case or performance limit, what are the most suitable degraded or shelter modes depending on the system and environment 's situation. The system should be able to react within a safe delay.</p>	Safety first for automated driving

Functional Requirements	Source
<p>The system should be able to perform a Minimum Risk Manoeuvre (MRM) in case of a system failure and reach a safe state with a tolerable level of risk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At L3: In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserve to orientate himself and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop. If possible, depending on the traffic situation and system capabilities, the reduced risk conditions will include the necessary lane changes to stop at the hard shoulder e.g. emergency lane or side of the road. • At L4: There is no request from the system to the driver to take over when the system is in normal operation area (i.e. on the motorway), so sleeping is allowed. In case a situation occurs, when average human driver would try to end the journey or simply stop at the motorway (e.g. extreme weather) and the driver does not take over, the system has the capability to leave the motorway and park the vehicle safely. 	<p>Safety first for automated driving</p>

TABLE 19: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS REGARDING KETS – HIGHWAY PILOT

Functional Requirements regarding KETs	Source
<p>Positioning: The system should be able to determine its location in relation to the ODD. The vehicle should be able to decide if it is inside or outside of a location-specific ODD.</p>	<p>Safety first for automated driving</p>
<p>V2X communication: in some cases, the ego can communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users to tell the future actions that it is going to take. This will help to fulfil traffic rules.</p>	<p>Safety first for automated driving</p>
<p>Cybersecurity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system supervisor’s architecture must be secured (redundancy, control ...) • The sensors detecting obstacles on the road must be verified and identified by the system supervisor. At least two different types of sensors should be used and controlling each other at all time. • V2I communication (toll gate & work zone) should be secured by the infrastructure owner (e.g. Vinci, APPR ...). • Over the air download and map cloud must be secured. 	<p>Safety first for automated driving</p>

3.2.3 Examples of abstract scenarios [adapted from MOOVE]

TABLE 20: LIST OF SCENARIOS - HIGHWAY PILOT

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Closest in path vehicle (CIPV) brakes	The ego vehicle is following its way behind the target vehicle when the target vehicle brakes.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the change in speed of the target vehicle. The ego vehicle must adapt its speed to keep a safe distance with the target vehicle.
Vehicle cut in front	A vehicle from an adjacent lane, moves to the ego vehicle lane, and becomes target vehicle in front.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle entering its lane. The ego must break and adapt its speed to respect a safe distance with the target vehicle.
Vehicle cut out front	The first in lane preceding vehicle, in front of ego vehicle, changes to an adjacent lane.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle exiting the lane. The ego must adapt its speed to keep a safe distance with the new target vehicle.
Vehicle cut through	While ego vehicle driving in lane with or without a preceding vehicle, a surrounding vehicle from an adjacent lane cut-in ego vehicle lane and without stopping cut-out to the adjacent lane on the other side of ego vehicle.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle entering and exiting the lane.
Vehicle front stopped in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching the target vehicle that is stopped in the ego lane (speed = 0 km/h),	The ego vehicle must be able to detect that the front vehicle is stopped. The ego vehicle must break in time and stop.
Static obstacle front in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching a static obstacle located on the lane.	The ego must be able to detect the type of obstacle (static obstacle, potentially mobile obstacle, mobile obstacle) The ego must be able to detect the speed of the obstacle.
Dynamic actor in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching a dynamic actor that is not motorized (e.g. pedestrian, cyclist, animal ...)	The ego must be able to detect the type of obstacle (static obstacle, potentially mobile obstacle, mobile obstacle) The ego must be able to detect the speed of the obstacle. The ego must be able to react to the trajectory of the dynamic actor to avoid accident.

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Ego follows its way (lateral risk)	<p>Free in lane driving without a preceding vehicle (in the sensor range, or in visibility) in the lane in front of ego vehicle.</p> <p>This scenario includes the possible work zone and the changes in the infrastructure (e.g. loss of lane marking, lane getting smaller, loss of lateral reference / guardrail ...)</p>	The ego should be able to detect changes in the road infrastructure (e.g. work zone...)
Ego changes lane	<p>The ego vehicle following its way in the lane.</p> <p>The ego vehicle changes lane by starting to overlap with the marking of the adjacent lane. The scenario ends when the ego vehicle has completely entered the new lane.</p>	<p>The ego should be able to detect, the lanes.</p> <p>The ego vehicle should be able to detect if other road users are approaching when changing lane.</p>
Ego overtakes	Ego vehicle is in the lane adjacent to the lane of a slower vehicle, and, overtakes the slower vehicle.	<p>The ego-vehicle should detect the position of the vehicle being overtaken.</p> <p>The ego should adapt its trajectory according to the actions of the target vehicle.</p>
Ego gives priority to emergency vehicle behind or motorbike	<p>The ego vehicle is following its lane when the target vehicle (emergency vehicle or motorbike) gets closer from behind.</p> <p>The ego vehicle adapts its position to facilitate the way of the target vehicle.</p> <p>The target vehicle overtakes the ego vehicle.</p>	<p>The ego vehicle should be able to detect the type of vehicle behind.</p> <p>The ego should be able to detect the speed of the vehicle following him.</p> <p>The ego vehicle should safely change lane or adapt its position in the lane to give way to the emergency vehicle / motorbike.</p>
Ego pass toll gate	<p>The ego-vehicle arrives in the toll gate area.</p> <p>We consider here the beginning of the scenario when the ego passes the first panel limiting speed to approach the toll gate.</p> <p>The ego-vehicle passes the toll gate entry</p> <p>The ego-vehicle exits the area, defined here, as the first speed-increasing panel. If this sign is not present in the first 500 meters, then the exit of the zone is defined as 500m after the gate.</p>	<p>The ego should be able to detect the changes in speed limit.</p> <p>The ego should be able to detect the toll gate.</p> <p>The ego should adapt its speed and enter the desired toll gate lane</p> <p>The ego should accelerate after passing the toll gate.</p>

3.2.4 Related projects and initiatives

TABLE 21: RELATION TO MOOVE

MOOVE	
Period	2015 - 2020
Status:	Ongoing
Context/Funding	French national funding
HEADSTART KETs	Positioning
HEADSTART Contact	VEDECOM, VALEO
Description	<p>Launched at the end of 2015, by VEDECOM, the MOOVE project aims to Identify real-world driving scenarios for the specification, validation and functional safety of CAD. A catalog of typical scenarios with their associated High-Level Parameters (HLP) is produced based on a database of real driving situations. These situations are recorded mainly on highway and open divided roadway in 15 European countries. Recordings are made in a wide variety of environmental and climatic conditions.</p> <p>The final goal of the MOOVE project is to provide a full representation of the ego vehicle environment to identify Safety Critical Scenarios (SCS).</p> <p>The real-world driving scenarios identified by MOOVE could be used in the future by other projects to build simulation tools for both the design and the validation of safe autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 1 million km recorded during approximately 20 000 hours of driving. • 29 functional scenarios identified and 90 safety relevant scenarios on highway and open divided roadway. <p>Participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEDECOM • OEM: PSA Peugeot Citroën, Renault • Tier 1: Valeo <p>ANR : Agence Nationale de la Recherche (French Government)</p>
Resources developed:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database of scenarios based on real driving situations. • 80 safety relevant scenarios identified. • Various High-Level Parameters (HLP) regarding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Road infrastructure ○ Ego vehicle ○ Obstacles ○ Climatic conditions
Documentation	<p>VEDECOM - Real world driving scenario identification for AV functional safety - Autonomous Vehicle Test & Development Symposium - 06/06/2018 - http://www.vedecom.fr/wp-content/uploads/AVS_SlidesShow_GildasTHIOLON_VEDECOM.pdf</p>

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TABLE 22: PEGASUS

PEGASUS	
Period	January 2016 – May 2019
Context/Funding	German, Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi)
HEADSTART KETs	Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	IKA, BAST
Description	<p>The PEGASUS project defines an overall testing and validation methodology for automated driving functions utilizing a scenario database.</p> <p>The overall objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of a standardized procedure for the testing and experimenting of automated vehicle systems in simulation, on test stands and in real environments. • Development of a continuous and flexible tool chain to safeguard the automated driving. • Integration of the tests in the development processes at an early stage. • Creation of a cross-manufacturer method for the safeguarding of highly automated driving functions.
Link	https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/home

TABLE 23: RELATION TO AUTOPILOT - HIGHWAY PILOT

AUTOPILOT	
Period	January 2017 – December 2019
Context/Funding	European project (H2020)
HEADSTART KETs	Cyber-security, Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	VEDECOM, ERTICO, IDIADA, TNO, CRF, VALEO, VICOMTECH

Description	<p>The overall objective of AUTOPILOT is to bring together relevant knowledge and technology from the automotive and the IoT value chains in order to develop IoT architectures and platforms which will bring automated driving towards a new dimension. Use cases: Urban driving, Automated Valet Parking, Highway Pilot, Platooning (V2V enabled).</p> <p>Pilot sites working on highway pilot are: Brainport/NL and Livorno/IT</p>
Link	https://autopilot-project.eu/

TABLE 24: RELATION TO ENABLE S3 - HIGHWAY PILOT

ENABLE-S3	
Period	May 2016 – May 2019
Context/Funding	ECSEL Joint Undertaking
HEADSTART KETs	Cyber-security, Communication (V2X), Positioning
HEADSTART Contact	TNO, VALEO, ViF, Toyota
Description	<p>European Initiative to Enable Validation for Highly Automated Safe and Secure Systems. The project developed a validation framework combining real-world tests with simulations, to be implemented in 6 different domains: automotive, aerospace, rail, maritime, health and farming. Using the framework should reduce the costs for testing of 1 project considerably, especially for highly automated systems.</p> <p>Use Cases: Highway Pilot, traffic jam pilot with different sensor systems, Indoor positioning for Valet parking, lane-vehicle following, intersection crossing with left-turn-assist and straight crossing.</p>
Link	https://www.enable-s3.eu/

TABLE 25: RELATION TO L3 PILOT - HIGHWAY PILOT

L3Pilot

Period	September 2017 –August 2021
Context/Funding	European project (H2020)
HEADSTART KETs	No
HEADSTART Contact	IKA, BAST, TNO, CRF, TME
Description	Automated driving is still the main focus of research activities in the European automotive industry. The European Commission’s flagship project “L3Pilot” is testing the viability of automated driving as a safe and efficient means of transportation and additionally exploring and promoting new service concepts to provide inclusive mobility. Therefore, L3Pilot will create a standardized Europe-wide piloting environment, coordinating activities across the piloting community in order to acquire data from 100 vehicles with 1000 drivers operating in 10 countries in Europe. Concluding, the project will evaluate the automated driving functions (ADFs), calculate the impacts and provide a cost-benefit analysis.
Link	https://www.l3pilot.eu/

TABLE 26: RELATION TO STREETWISE

StreetWise 	
Context/Funding	TNO activity supported by several internal and external project and activities
HEADSTART Contact	TNO
Description	<p>StreetWise : Scenario-Based Safety Validation Of Connected And Automated Driving</p> <p>StreetWise is a data-driven methodology that provides real-world scenarios and test cases for the development and assessment of advanced driver assistance systems and (connected) automated driving systems. The core of the method is a database in which all parameterized scenarios are stored that have been identified from driving data that is collected from the various fleets of data collection vehicles. This can be either test vehicles, prototype vehicles or production vehicles that drive on the public road collecting data with their state-of-the-art ADAS or (C)AD sensor sets.</p>

	<p>Research activities for this project include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extension towards diverse operational design domains Scenarios with multiple active actors Scenarios for connected vehicles Large scale scenario sharing Test case generation Completeness of the scenario database Safety assessment framework
Link	https://publications.tno.nl/publication/34626550/AyT8Zc/TNO-2018-streetwise.pdf

3.2.5 General assessment of HEADSTART requirements collection

The HEADSTART requirements that apply to the Highway pilot use case are from the following categories:

Definition and availability of scenarios: Scenarios from a database need to be available and match the highway pilot use case ODD. The scenario concept used must be aligned with the overall methodology and support the ODD on all 6 layers.

Requirements on collaboration partners: Formal arrangements must be made with other projects in order to sharing test data and results. The collaboration must be possible until the end of 2021 for the final event of HEADSTART.

Model-based testing: The Functional description of the CAD-function must be available as a code (for SiL/MiL) and on target HW (ECU) (for HiL). Additionally, necessary models for simulation are depended on the actual driving function, which needs to be tested. This includes either models or at the very minimum basic information about the sensor setup (mostly the used sensor with their respective field-of-view) as well as information about the vehicle itself (most importantly mass and dimension).

Physical Testing - proving ground: Necessary requirements for proving ground include the maximum speed allowed to test this use case because scenarios should address realistic situations and parameters of the use case. The proving ground lanes must be easy to repaint, and meteorological situations included in the scenario should be available.

Physical Testing - field operational tests (FOT): Driver impact and impact of other road users need to be taken into account during the FOT. The system behavior needs to be compared to baseline condition, this needs to be defined prior to the test (SAE L0, L1 or L2). Finally, the test conditions (road type, infrastructure, traffic, weather, etc.) should be standardized to allow comparison between different vehicles.

Relevance to key user groups - type approval: The requirements on type approval are various and most of them are relevant for the highway pilot use case. First, the technical documentation provided by the OEM must be well described including the limits of the function's ODD. This will allow the identification of edge cases to test. The test track of the proving ground must be adapted to the system being evaluated.

Technical service and OEM must go together during the development phase to fulfill the functional safety requirements. Suitable Test-Tools need to be robust and available on the proving grounds.

Full system functionality must be available on proving ground. For the highway use cases, geo-fencing is necessary.

Relevance to key user groups - consumer testing: For consumer testing the use case should have a clear safety benefit on road injuries. Since safety is ensured by type approval, typical consumer testing should focus on other criteria such as HMI, ODD or Comfort assessment. Minimum Risk Maneuver (MRM) implemented in the function logic should address risky situations in case of driver unavailability for the level 4 and 5.

Testability of KETs: The main KET for the highway pilot use case is the positioning of the vehicle. Depending on the function, V2X communication and cyber-security can be a priority as well. An example of the use of V2X communication can be the toll gate passing with V2I communication.

Communication: To enable testing of communication, the function must utilize communication with low latency and high reliability. Since the focus in HEADSTART is on the operational layer, the communication usage must be in the operational layer. The testing of V2X communications must be focused on secured communications. For V2I communication, the infrastructures should be available for testing.

Cybersecurity

Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) activity to be carried out as part of the cybersecurity lifecycle (involving the CAD-function of the VUT). Cybersecurity testing highly depends on actions to be done in the design phase of a vehicle or function. Finally, models and tools must be available to rank cybersecurity.

3.3 Traffic Jam Chauffeur

3.3.1 Description

The traffic jam chauffeur use case can be defined as conditional driving automation (L3) in traffic jam conditions, on highways and other structurally separated roads, with a speed range of 0 to 60 km/h. Traffic Jam Chauffeur is capable of keeping the vehicle in the current lane and maintaining a safe distance to the vehicle in front of the ego vehicle. In some cases, the function will also be able to support lane changes.

The driver must deliberately activate the system but does not have to monitor the system constantly. The driver can at all times override or switch off the system. In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserve to orientate himself and take over the driving task (typically 10 seconds). In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop.²

The traffic jam chauffeur can be enhanced with information coming through V2X communications, cyber security and preventing hacking is also an important aspect of this use case. The main benefits of this use case for the consumers are the added comfort while driving as well as an increased safety.

² Adapted from ERTRAC roadmap <https://www.ertrac.org/uploads/documentsearch/id57/ERTRAC-CAD-Roadmap-2019.pdf>

Area of application

TABLE 27: AREA OF APPLICATION - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

Entry	Value	Comment
Area of operation	Open Roads, mixed traffic	
Road Type	<p>Highway or other structurally separated roads: Other characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No traffic in the opposite direction on the road (structurally separated roads) • limited access: strictly motorized vehicles and trucks (No pedestrian or cyclist) • With or without toll gate • No intersections and no traffic lights (except some tunnels or bridges). 	
Admissible Road Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roads, tunnels, vicinity of highway entry/exit, overpasses • No work zone 	
Dedicated infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear lane markings (e.g. with reflective paint) and visible road signs are needed • No connectivity V2I needed but possible (e.g. toll gate or work zone warning) • Potholes cancellation • HD MAP with regular updates (future development) 	
Traffic Density	Traffic jam Chauffeur= -20% of maximum speed (e.g. speed < 104 km/h on a highway with 130km/h max speed)	
Speed Range	From 0 km/h to 110 km/h	
Environmental Conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Min visibility of X, → no fog, no snow (no use of fog lamp) • Min friction coef. of Y → no heavy rain and snow • The vehicle cannot drive under extreme weather condition (heavy rain, snow, fog ...) • The function can work both in day and night time 	
Vehicle Configuration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger cars with a maximum gross vehicle mass up to 3 500 kg • Truck with a mass of 12 to 44 t. 	

Reliance of KETs identified in HEADSTART

TABLE 28: RELIANCE OF KETS IN HEADSTART - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

KET	Function's usage
Communication	Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication is not necessary for this use case. An example of an application of communicationV2X for this use case could be a vehicle in front of the closest in path vehicle sending a signal to warn other road users that it is braking.
Positioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-lane positioning used for lateral control, • Relative inter-vehicle positioning for distance keeping with other road users and longitudinal control, • Absolute positioning (through GNSS and Maps) e.g. for deciding gaps and speeds due to environmental and zone conditions
Cyber Security	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The sensors detecting obstacles on the road must be verified and identified by the system supervisor. At least two different types of sensors should be used and controlling each other. • V2I communication (toll gate & work zone) should be secured by the infrastructure owner (e.g. Vinci, APPR ...) • The system supervisor's architecture must be secured (redundancy, control ...) • Over the air download and map cloud must be secured as well.

3.3.2 Representative scenario - "Closest in path vehicle brakes" [Adapted from MOOVE]

This functional scenario corresponds to the real-life situation where the ego-vehicle is:

- Following a target vehicle in its lane (presence of a closest in path vehicle (CIPV))
- The vehicle does not change lane

Events and actions:

- The target vehicle in front of the ego-vehicle brakes.
- Associated scenarios cover target vehicle braking due to:
 - A busy lane
 - A late exit
 - Low adherence or visibility

Initial condition

The ego vehicle is following the target vehicle.

Event: The target vehicle starts braking.

Sequence of scenes

TABLE 29: SEQUENCE OF SCENES - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

#	Description	Illustration
1	Target vehicle starts braking	
2	The ego vehicle adapts its speed to keep a safe distance with the target vehicle	
3	<p>The acceleration of the target vehicle goes back to $\sim 0 \text{ m/s}^2$ Which means that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The target vehicle stops braking and keep/or/ The target vehicle is completely stopped in the lane. 	

Terminal condition

The target vehicle has stopped braking and carries on in the lane /or/ the target vehicle is completely stopped in the lane.

Functional Requirements

TABLE 30: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

Functional Requirements	Source
<p>Determine location: The system should be able to determine its location in relation to the ODD. The vehicle should be able to decide if it is inside or outside of a location-specific ODD. The location in the ODD may be required, depending on the item definition.</p>	Safety first for automated driving [9]
<p>Perceive relevant static and dynamic objects in proximity to the automated vehicle: All entities that an automated driving system requires for its functional behaviour should be perceived. The highest priority is placed on entities with an associated risk of collision. Sample entities include dynamic objects (e.g. (vulnerable) road users and characteristics of the respective movement), static instances (e.g. road boundaries, traffic guidance and communication signals) and obstacles.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Predict the future behaviour of relevant objects in order to create a forecast of the environment. The intention of the relevant objects should be interpreted in order to form the basis for predicting future motion.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Create a collision-free and lawful driving plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Maintain a safe lateral and longitudinal distance to other objects. Comply with all applicable traffic rules within the ODD. Consider potential areas where objects may be occluded. In unclear situations the right of way is given, not taken. If a crash can be avoided without endangering third parties, traffic rules may be prioritized if necessary. 	Safety first for automated driving

Functional Requirements	Source
<p>Correctly execute the driving plan: The corresponding actuation signals for lateral and longitudinal control should be generated based on the driving plan.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users Automated driving vehicles are required to communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users, depending on the ODD and the use cases</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>Determine if specified nominal performance is not achieved: Any element of the automated driving system can, either on its own or in combination with others, result in adverse behaviour. Therefore, mechanisms are required to detect the adverse nominal performance of the system. Typical aspects for influencing the nominal performance are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unwanted human factors, including misuse and manipulations • Deviation of the intended functionality • Technological limitations • Environmental conditions • Systematic and random failure modes 	Safety first for automated driving
<p>In case of failure or at the limit of performance, the system should be able to reach a degraded mode or shelter mode. Define for each failure case or performance limit, what are the most suitable degraded or shelter modes depending on the system and environments situation. The system should be able to react within a safe delay.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>The system should be able to perform a Minimum Risk Manoeuvre (MRM) in case of a system failure and reach a safe state with a tolerable level of risk.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At L3: In case of a takeover request to the driver from the system, the driver has sufficient time reserve to orientate himself and take over the driving task. In case the driver does not take over, the system will go to a reduced risk condition, i.e. bring the vehicle to a safe stop. If possible, depending on the traffic situation and system capabilities, the reduced risk conditions will include the necessary lane changes to stop at the hard shoulder e.g. emergency lane or side of the road. • At L4: There is no request from the system to the driver to take over when the system is in normal operation area (i.e. on the motorway), so sleeping is allowed. In case a situation occurs, when average human driver would try to end the journey or simply stop at the motorway (e.g. extreme weather) and the driver does not take over, the system has the capability to leave the motorway and park the vehicle safely. 	Safety first for automated driving

TABLE 31: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS REGARDING KETS - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

Functional Requirements regarding KETs	Source
<p>Positioning: The system should be able to determine its location in relation to the ODD. The vehicle should be able to decide if it is inside or outside of a location-specific ODD.</p>	Safety first for automated driving
<p>V2X communication: in some cases, the ego can communicate and interact with other (vulnerable) road users to tell the future actions that it is going to take. This will help to fulfil traffic rules.</p>	Safety first for automated driving

Functional Requirements regarding KETs	Source
<p>Cybersecurity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The system supervisor's architecture must be secured (redundancy, control ...) • The sensors detecting obstacles on the road must be verified and identified by the system supervisor. At least two different types of sensors should be used and controlling each other at all time. • V2I communication (toll gate & work zone) should be secured by the infrastructure owner (e.g. Vinci, APPR ...). • Over the air download and map cloud must be secured. 	<p>Safety first for automated driving</p>

3.3.3 Example of abstract scenarios [adapted from MOOVE]

TABLE 32: LIST OF SCENARIOS - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Closest in path vehicle (CIPV) brakes	The ego vehicle is following its way behind the target vehicle when the target vehicle brakes.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the change in speed of the target vehicle. The ego vehicle must adapt its speed to keep a safe distance with the target vehicle.
Vehicle cut in front	A vehicle from an adjacent lane, moves to the ego vehicle lane, and becomes target vehicle in front.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle entering its lane. The ego must break and adapt its speed to respect a safe distance with the target vehicle.
Vehicle cut out front	The first in lane preceding vehicle, in front of ego vehicle, changes to an adjacent lane.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle exiting the lane. The ego must adapt its speed to keep a safe distance with the new target vehicle.
Vehicle cut through	While ego vehicle driving in lane with or without a preceding vehicle, a surrounding vehicle from an adjacent lane cut-in ego vehicle lane and without stopping cut-out to the adjacent lane on the other side of ego vehicle.	The ego vehicle must be able to detect the target vehicle entering and exiting the lane.
Vehicle front stopped in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching the target vehicle that is stopped in the ego lane (speed = 0 km/h),	The ego vehicle must be able to detect that the front vehicle is stopped. The ego vehicle must break in time and stop.
Static obstacle front in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching a static obstacle located on the lane.	The ego must be able to detect the type of obstacle (static obstacle, potentially mobile obstacle, mobile obstacle) The ego must be able to detect the speed of the obstacle.
Dynamic actor in ego lane	The ego is following its way in its lane and is approaching a dynamic actor that is not motorized (e.g. pedestrian, cyclist, animal ...)	The ego must be able to detect the type of obstacle (static obstacle, potentially mobile obstacle, mobile obstacle) The ego must be able to detect the speed of the obstacle. The ego must be able to react to the trajectory of the dynamic actor to avoid accident.

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Ego follows its way (lateral risk)	<p>Free in lane driving without a preceding vehicle (in the sensor range, or in visibility) in the lane in front of ego vehicle.</p> <p>This scenario includes the possible work zone and the changes in the infrastructure (e.g. loss of lane marking, lane getting smaller, loss of lateral reference / guardrail ...)</p>	<p>The ego should be able to detect changes in the road infrastructure (e.g. work zone...)</p>
Ego changes lane	<p>The ego vehicle following its way in the lane.</p> <p>The ego vehicle changes lane by starting to overlap with the marking of the adjacent lane. The scenario ends when the ego vehicle has completely entered the new lane.</p>	<p>The ego should be able to detect, the lanes.</p> <p>The ego vehicle should be able to detect if other road users are approaching when changing lane.</p>
Ego overtakes	<p>Ego vehicle is in the lane adjacent to the lane of a slower vehicle, and, overtakes the slower vehicle.</p>	<p>The ego-vehicle should detect the position of the vehicle being overtaken.</p> <p>The ego should adapt its trajectory according to the actions of the target vehicle.</p>
Ego gives priority to emergency vehicle behind or motorbike	<p>The ego vehicle is following its lane when the target vehicle (emergency vehicle or motorbike) gets closer from behind.</p> <p>The ego vehicle adapts its position to facilitate the way of the target vehicle.</p> <p>The target vehicle overtakes the ego vehicle.</p>	<p>The ego vehicle should be able to detect the type of vehicle behind.</p> <p>The ego should be able to detect the speed of the vehicle following him.</p> <p>The ego vehicle should safely change lane or adapt its position in the lane to give way to the emergency vehicle / motorbike.</p>

3.3.4 Related projects and initiatives

TABLE 33: RELATION TO MOOVE - TRAFFIC JAM CHAUFFEUR

MOOVE	
Period	2015 - 2020
Status:	Ongoing
Context/Funding	French national funding
HEADSTART KETs	Positioning
HEADSTART Contact	VEDECOM, VALEO
Description	<p>Launched at the end of 2015, by VEDECOM, the MOOVE project aims to Identify real-world driving scenarios for the specification, validation and functional safety of CAD. A catalogue of typical scenarios with their associated High-Level Parameters (HLP) is produced based on a database of real driving situations. These situations are recorded mainly on highway and open divided roadway in 15 European countries. Recordings are made in a wide variety of environmental and climatic conditions.</p> <p>The final goal of the MOOVE project is to provide a full representation of the ego vehicle environment to identify Safety Critical Scenarios (SCS).</p> <p>The real-world driving scenarios identified by MOOVE could be used in the future by other projects to build simulation tools for both the design and the validation of safe autonomous vehicles.</p> <p>Results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 1 million km recorded during approximately 20 000 hours of driving. • 29 functional scenarios identified and 90 safety relevant scenarios on highway and open divided roadway. <p>Participants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VEDECOM • OEM: PSA Peugeot Citroën, Renault • Tier 1: Valeo <p>ANR : Agence Nationale de la Recherche (French Government)</p>
Resources developed:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Database of scenarios based on real driving situations. • 80 safety relevant scenarios identified. • Various High-Level Parameters (HLP) regarding: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Road infrastructure ○ Ego vehicle ○ Obstacles ○ Climatic conditions
Documentation	<p>VEDECOM - Real world driving scenario identification for AV functional safety - Autonomous Vehicle Test & Development Symposium - 06/06/2018 - http://www.vedecom.fr/wp-content/uploads/AVS_SlidesShow_GildasTHIOLON_VEDECOM.pdf</p>

For more information, please contact Annie Bracquemond (annie.bracquemond@vedecom.fr)

TABLE 34: PEGASUS

PEGASUS	
Period	January 2016 – May 2019
Context/Funding	German, Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi)
HEADSTART KETs	Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	IKA, BAST
Description	<p>The PEGASUS project defines an overall testing and validation methodology for automated driving functions utilizing a scenario database.</p> <p>The overall objectives of the project are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of a standardized procedure for the testing and experimenting of automated vehicle systems in simulation, on test stands and in real environments. • Development of a continuous and flexible tool chain to safeguard the automated driving. • Integration of the tests in the development processes at an early stage. • Creation of a cross-manufacturer method for the safeguarding of highly automated driving functions.
Link	https://www.pegasusprojekt.de/en/home

TABLE 35: L3 PILOT

L3Pilot	
Period	September 2017 – August 2021
Context/Funding	European project (H2020)
HEADSTART KETs	No

HEADSTART Contact	IKA, BAST, TNO, CRF, TME
Description	Automated driving is still the main focus of research activities in the European automotive industry. The European Commission's flagship project "L3Pilot" is testing the viability of automated driving as a safe and efficient means of transportation and additionally exploring and promoting new service concepts to provide inclusive mobility. Therefore, L3Pilot will create a standardized Europe-wide piloting environment, coordinating activities across the piloting community in order to acquire data from 100 vehicles with 1000 drivers operating in 10 countries in Europe. Concluding, the project will evaluate the automated driving functions (ADFs), calculate the impacts and provide a cost-benefit analysis.
Link	https://www.l3pilot.eu/

TABLE 36: STREETWISE

<div style="background-color: #1a3d54; color: white; padding: 5px;"> <p>StreetWise</p> </div>	
Context/Funding	TNO activity supported by several internal and external project and activities
HEADSTART Contact	TNO
Description	<p>StreetWise : Scenario-Based Safety Validation Of Connected And Automated Driving</p> <p>StreetWise is a data-driven methodology that provides real-world scenarios and test cases for the development and assessment of advanced driver assistance systems and (connected) automated driving systems. The core of the method is a database in which all parameterized scenarios are stored that have been identified from driving data that is collected from the various fleets of data collection vehicles. This can be either test vehicles, prototype vehicles or production vehicles that drive on the public road collecting data with their state-of-the-art ADAS or (C)AD sensor sets.</p> <p>Research activities for this project include :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extension towards diverse operational design domains • Scenarios with multiple active actors • Scenarios for connected vehicles • Large scale scenario sharing • Test case generation • Completeness of the scenario database • Safety assessment framework

Link	https://publications.tno.nl/publication/34626550/AyT8Zc/TNO-2018-streetwise.pdf
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3.3.5 General assessment of HEADSTART requirements collection

The HEADSTART requirements that apply to the Traffic Jam Chauffeur use case are the same as for the Highway pilot for the following categories:

- **Definition and availability of scenarios**
- **Requirements on collaboration partners**
- **Model-based testing**
- **Physical Testing - proving ground**
- **Physical Testing - Field operational tests (FOT)**
- **Relevance to key user groups - Type approval**
- **Relevance to key user groups - Consumer testing**

Testability of KETs: Similar to highway pilot, the traffic jam use case mainly relies on the positioning of the vehicle. Depending on the function, V2X communication can be used for and cyber-security can be a priority as well. An example of V2X communication for this use case can be the V2V warning of another car (positioned several cars in front of the ego) starting to brake.

Communication: To enable testing of communication, the function must utilize communication with low latency and high reliability. Since the focus in HEADSTART is on the operational layer, the communication usage must be in the operational layer. The testing of V2X communications must be focused on secured communications. For V2I communication, the infrastructures should be available for testing.

Cybersecurity: Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) activity to be carried out as part of the cybersecurity lifecycle (involving the CAD-function of the VUT). Cybersecurity testing highly depends on actions to be done in the design phase of a vehicle or function. Finally, Models and tools must be available to rank cybersecurity.

3.4 Valet Parking

3.4.1 Description

Automated Valet Parking (AVP) is a process where a vehicle is able to park or unpark by itself without human intervention, as is the case in the conventional valet parking. In most situations, the human driver is able to leave the car at some predefined drop-off location and retrieve it once they need it back. The operations of parking and manoeuvring the car in the parking area (indoors or outdoors), retrieving it, and possibly other additional services are managed by the parking management system.

The user leaves their car close to the entrance of a parking lot. Then the vehicle drives itself within the parking lot to find a spot, using driving functions mapping the environment via integrated sensors and/or IoT infrastructure. When the user desires to leave, they make a call (e.g. via an app/smartphone) and the vehicle follows the reverse route from the parking lot to the entrance, to be delivered to the driver.

Area of application

TABLE 37: AREA OF APPLICATION – VALET PARKING

Entry	Value	Comment
Area of operation	Indoors parking lot, outdoors parking lot, roadside dedicated parking	
Road Type	Conventional parking lot conditions	
Admissible Road Infrastructure	Open road, closed space building parking lot (underground, ground level or 1st floor)	
Dedicated infrastructure	Clearly painted parking spots, in-vehicle sensors, parking spot detection sensors, cameras, V2X connectivity, indoors network coverage, outdoors GNSS coverage	
Traffic Density	Low to zero traffic, low to zero pedestrian existence, no motorcycles/trucks (only cars)	
Speed Range	< 15 km/h	
Environmental Conditions	No weather restrictions in indoors parking, not working in extreme weather conditions	
Vehicle Configuration	Passenger cars with a maximum gross vehicle mass up to 3 500 kg with dedicated in-vehicle sensors to support AVP	

Reliance of KETs identified in HEADSTART

TABLE 38: RELIANCE ON KETs – VALET PARKING

KET	Function's usage
Communication	AVP concept is based on V2I communication. Moreover, V2V communication shall be explicitly established. In general, V2X communication is necessary.
Positioning	The automated vehicle uses driving functions based on knowledge about the environment around the vehicle. This means that it maps the surrounding environment acknowledging the position of other users (e.g. vehicles, pedestrians) and the location of empty and full parking places, thus positioning is necessary for digital navigation.
Cyber Security	It is not a major requirement for AVP to function properly. Of course, all security measures concerning communication and positioning shall apply to avoid errors or crashes.

3.4.2 Representative scenario - Car automatedly valet parks indoors

Initial condition

User drops-off their car in front of an indoors parking lot

Sequence of scenes

TABLE 39: SEQUENCE OF SCENES – VALET PARKING REPRESENTATIVE SCENARIO

#	Description
1	Driver leaves the car in front of the parking lot
2	Car automatically starts to move inside the parking lot
3	Car communicates with parking infrastructure and identifies empty spots
4	A proposed trip is planned towards an empty spot
5	Car proceeds with required manoeuvres following the chosen trip
6	Once reached the empty spot, the car proceeds with parking manoeuvres

Terminal condition

The car is parked within the identified empty spot in the indoors parking lot.

Functional Requirements

TABLE 40: FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS – VALET PARKING REPRESENTATIVE SCENARIO

Functional Requirements [NON EXHAUSTIVE, FOR ILLUSTRATION]	Source
V2I communication shall be established, including communication to the integrated IoT platforms running within the parking lot	Autopilot project
Identification of empty spots via cameras and/or parking lot sensors	Autopilot project
Dynamic calculation of a (best) trip plan towards an empty parking spot	Autopilot project
Ability to maneuver during the trip and while parking the car	Autopilot project
Detection of other users in the parking, including vulnerable road users (pedestrians), legacy vehicles or other automated vehicles	Autopilot project
Ability to re-arrange the trip according to circumstances / obstacles detected	Autopilot project

Functional Requirements [NON EXHAUSTIVE, FOR ILLUSTRATION]	Source
Map the parking lot and constantly ensure positioning even without the usage of GNSS	Autopilot project
In cases of error or malfunction in the system to ensure the safe stop and collision free remaining trip of the car	Autopilot project

3.4.3 Examples of abstract scenarios

TABLE 41: LIST OF SCENARIOS – VALET PARKING

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Car automatedly valet parks outdoors [general case]	Driver drops-off their car in a parking lot which is open-aired, thus providing more capabilities for connectivity (e.g. GNSS support). The vehicle follows the same rules like the indoors scenario.	Establish V2X communication, identify empty spots, dynamically calculate best trip plan, ability to manoeuvre, detect other road users, ability to follow trip and/or re-arrange trip, use GNSS for ensuring positioning, proceed to safe mitigation measures when malfunction occurs
Car automatedly valet parks on the road side outdoors	Driver drops-off their car in the road and the vehicle follows the same rules like the indoors scenario towards parking in a pre-defined side road section.	Establish V2X communication, identify empty side road spots, dynamically calculate best trip plan, ability to manoeuvre, detect other road users, ability to follow trip and/or re-arrange trip, use GNSS for ensuring positioning, proceed to safe mitigation measures when malfunction occurs
Route to parking spot obstructed by other vehicles	While calculating the best route towards the empty spot, the car is blocked by another car	The car needs to instantly re-calculate a new / alternative trip, or inform the parking management system in case it has reached a deadlock

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
Unable to park in assigned spot	The initially identified spot is actually not feasible for parking (e.g. too narrow)	Confirm the parking spot availability prior to launching the parking manoeuvre
User calls car to retrieve from parking	Using an integrated app, the driver of the car informs the parking management system that they intent to deliver the car	Parking management application available and able to manage the “calls” from the users and to supervise the delivery of the appropriate car to the right user
Interaction with other users	The car meets other legacy or automated cars in the trip to park or unpark, or even pedestrians (e.g. drivers of legacy cars within the parking lot).	Detection of other users, adjustment of trip dynamically to park/unpark, fulfilment of traffic regulations and safety rules within the parking lot

3.4.4 Related projects and initiatives

TABLE 42: LEITINITIATIVE

Project: LEITINITIATIVE	
Duration:	Period: July 2019 – June 2022
Context/founding:	VDA German project
HEADSTART KETs:	Positioning, Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	VALEO
Description:	<p>Project is focused on L4 Valet parking. Objectives are :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development and demonstration of L4 Parking with target to reach TRL 7 - Definition of certification process of L4 parking system (Vehicle+ Infrastructure) - Definition of validation strategy for L4 driving with use case parking

Link <https://www.eict.de/en/projects/>

TABLE 43: AUTOPILOT

Project: Autopilot	
Duration:	Period: January 2017 – December 2019
Context/funding:	European project (H2020)
HEADSTART KETs:	Cyber-security, Communication (V2X)
HEADSTART Contact	VEDECOM, ERTICO, IDIADA, TNO, CRF, VALEO, VICOMTECH
Description:	<p>The overall objective of AUTOPILOT is to bring together relevant knowledge and technology from the automotive and the IoT value chains in order to develop IoT architectures and platforms which will bring automated driving towards a new dimension. Use cases: Urban driving, Automated Valet Parking, Highway Pilot, Platooning (V2V enabled).</p> <p>Regarding Valet Parking there have been 4 pilots working on that Use Case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finland, Tampere, Parking lot (50 cars) - France, Versailles, Road-side dedicated parking - Netherlands, Brainport, Parking lot (180 cars) - Spain, Vigo, Parking garage (200 cars)
Link	https://autopilot-project.eu/

TABLE 44: ENABLE-S3

Project: ENABLE-S3	
Duration:	May 2016 – May 2019

Project: ENABLE-S3

Context/founding:	ECSEL Joint Undertaking
HEADSTART KETs:	Cyber-security, Communication (V2X), Positioning
HEADSTART Contact	TNO, VALEO, ViF, Toyota
Description:	<p>European Initiative to Enable Validation for Highly Automated Safe and Secure Systems. The project developed a validation framework combining real-world tests with simulations, to be implemented in 6 different domains: automotive, aerospace, rail, maritime, health and farming. Using the framework should reduce the costs for testing of 1 project considerably, especially for highly automated systems.</p> <p>Use Cases: Highway Pilot, traffic jam pilot with different sensor systems, In-door positioning for Valet parking, lane-vehicle following, intersection crossing with left-turn-assist and straight crossing.</p> <p>Regarding Valet Parking, two main demonstrators are piloted within the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Demonstrator 1: “Integrated Virtual Demonstrator and Test” with four main compartments: Test management, Test platform, System Under Test (SUT) and Integration. - Demonstrator 2: “Indoor Vehicle Localization” with three main different technological approaches regarding positioning: Bluetooth Low Energy Method, Camera Sensors, Lidar Sensors.
Link	https://www.enable-s3.eu/

3.4.5 General assessment of HEADSTART requirements collection

The Valet Parking use case is mostly based on V2X communications and positioning of the vehicle, while cyber-security is not regarded as priority for the conduction of existing pilot demonstrations. Communication shall be high throughput and low latency, while the parking infrastructure shall include several sensors (cameras, motion sensors, parking lot sensors), the vehicle shall be equipped with on-board sensors (ultrasonic, cameras, radars, lidars...) and SW bricks for other road user detection. Moreover, positioning techniques shall support the pilot including constant mapping of the environment, issuing a proper trip towards parking/unparking the vehicle and supporting GNSS coverage wherever applicable.

3.5 Urban Automated Shuttle

3.5.1 Description

Urban Automated Shuttle is a current trend promoted by local authorities, regions or even large organizations (e.g. airports, campuses) to serve the rising needs of citizens or users, covering as much as possible the last mile mobility necessity. The most characteristic example is the usage from cities/pilots, which inspect their current transport bus services and strive to include novel automated bus lines to cover existing needs in specific sectors. In general, the approach is more or less common in all cases, including the conduction of a feasibility study, implementation study, infrastructure adaptation, acquisition and adaptation of automated buses prior to the actualization of the (pilot) automated shuttle operation.

Area of application

TABLE 45: AREA OF APPLICATION – URBAN AUTOMATED SHUTTLE

Entry	Value	Comment
Area of operation	Municipal/regional road tissue, closed campus, airport premises	
Road Type	Open road, other road type users (from pedestrians to cyclists and trucks)	
Admissible Road Infrastructure	Intersections, bridges, traffic lights	
Dedicated infrastructure	Segregated, semi-segregated or non-segregated lanes (lane should at least be painted whenever not segregated), smart traffic lights to promote green wave movement, dedicated control center monitoring parts of the route and the inside of the shuttle (respecting GDPR issues), on-board cameras, lidars, V2X connectivity, GNSS coverage	
Traffic Density	It ranges per case and could involve from protected campuses to real life traffic conditions within a city network	
Speed Range	< 50 km/h	
Environmental Conditions	Not working in extreme weather conditions	
Vehicle Configuration	Automated mini bus of ~ 10 seats equipped with sensors, cameras, lidars	

Reliance of KETs identified in HEADSTART

TABLE 46 RELIANCE ON KETs – URBAN AUTOMATED SHUTTLE

KET	Function's usage
Communication	V2X is necessary for the operation of the pilot. The automated shuttle should keep constant communication to the control center, since in most cases it is prerequisite for the legal framework to be valid while operating.
Positioning	The shuttle has to constantly acknowledge its positioning in the operating route and proceed to emergency actions (e.g emergency stop) when deviating for any reason.
Cyber Security	Although important, not the first priority to operate in this use case, since the main focus is the operation even without reaching all cyber security thresholds.

3.5.2 Representative scenario

Initial condition

Automated shuttle stops in a bus stop crowded with waiting passengers to embark on it.

Sequence of scenes

TABLE 47: SEQUENCE OF SCENES – URBAN AUTOMATED SHUTTLE REPRESENTATIVE SCENARIO

#	Description
1	Shuttle locates the safety disembarkation bus stop zone and opens the side doors.
2	Shuttle assures that passengers have embarked and closes the side doors
3	Shuttle checks lane condition and starts accelerating away from the bus stop
4	Shuttle receives request for disembarkation while on the move
5	Shuttle identifies next target bus stop
6	Shuttle slows down towards the target bus stop
7	Shuttle stops in the target bus stop

Terminal condition

The shuttle opens the side doors and passengers inside the shuttle disembark to the preferred bus stop

Functional Requirements

TABLE 48 FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS – URBAN AUTOMATED SHUTTLE REPRESENTATIVE SCENARIO

Functional Requirements [NON EXHAUSTIVE, FOR ILLUSTRATION]	Source
Ability to follow the selected route and stay within the lane of operation	CityMobil2 project
Constant communication to the control center via several means to ensure V2X communication (ITS-G5, 4G/LTE, 5G/LTE)	CityMobil2 project
Ensure GNSS coverage throughout the route for constant confirmation of the vehicle's positioning	CityMobil2 project
In case of malfunction in communication ensure safe stop	CityMobil2 project
Ability to recognize other Road Side Users (pedestrians, cyclists, cars, motorcycles, trucks)	CityMobil2 project
Recognize obstacles inside and near the trajectory	CityMobil2 project
Ability to maneuver deviating an obstacle	CityMobil2 project
Ability to recognize traffic lights	CityMobil2 project
Respect priority in intersections	CityMobil2 project
Respect priority in traffic lights	CityMobil2 project
Recognize pre-determined automated bus stops	CityMobil2 project
Safely stop in the automated bus stop zone	CityMobil2 project
Safely conduct the embarkation and disembarkation process	CityMobil2 project
Provide remote ability for emergency stop	CityMobil2 project
Provide on-board ability for emergency stop	CityMobil2 project

3.5.3 Examples of abstract scenarios

TABLE 49: LIST OF SCENARIOS – URBAN AUTOMATED SHUTTLE

Scenario name	Description	Functional requirements
On-demand call for shuttle	Passenger/user may arrange on-demand operation of the shuttle for pre-defined routes via an application	Application for management of routes, on-line communication of the vehicle, the management system, the control centre and the vehicle in an integrated way
Shuttle deviates from route	Due to obstacle in trajectory the shuttle has to deviate	Obstacle detection, neighbouring lane control, maneuver ability, respect of traffic regulations
Shuttle crosses intersection	The vehicle reaches an intersection on its route	On-road sign detection and identification, other RSU detection and identification, respect of traffic regulations
Shuttle crosses traffic light intersection	The vehicle reaches a traffic light intersection on its route	Traffic light detection and identification, communication with the smart traffic light system, other RSU detection and identification, respect of traffic regulations
Shuttle loses communication with control center	The shuttle loses communication with the control center for various reasons (e.g technical malfunction, power supply interruption, etc.)	Immediate confirmation of communication loss, safe halt of the vehicle

3.5.4 Related projects and initiatives

TABLE 50: AVENUE

AVENUE	
Duration:	May 2018 – April 2022
Context/Funding:	H2020
HEADSTART KETs	V2X communication, positioning
HEADSTART contact	VIF
Description:	<p>The target of the AVENUE project is to demonstrate and pilot the adaptability and efficiency of the deployment of small and medium autonomous vehicles (AV's) in Lyon, Luxembourg, Geneva, Copenhagen and 2-3 replicator cities as of the 3d year of the project. The AVENUE vision for future public transport in urban and suburban areas, is that autonomous vehicles will ensure safe, rapid, economic, sustainable and personalised transport of passengers, while minimising vehicle changes. The goal is to provide door to door autonomous transport allowing commuters to benefit from autonomous vehicles.</p>
Link:	https://h2020-avenue.eu/

TABLE 51: GALILEO 4 MOBILITY

Galileo 4 Mobility	
Duration:	January 2018 – June 2020
Context/Funding:	H2020 Mobility for Growth, GNSS Agency
HEADSTART KETs	Positioning
HEADSTART contact	PILDO

Galileo 4 Mobility

Description:

The project aims to 1) understand, define and validate which are the requirements for GNSS-Galileo in MaaS, 2) develop the key elements to exploit Galileo benefits within the MaaS sector, 3) disseminate the project results and support their exploitation after the project lifetime.

Five operational demonstrators will be undertaken in the project – in Barcelona (three pilot sites, of which one pending), Thessaloniki, and Paris. Of interest to the Urban Automated Shuttle is the Barcelona Pilot Site named “Public Transport on Demand”.

Link:

<http://www.galileo4mobility.eu/>

TABLE 52: AVINT

AVINT

Duration:

June 2018 – June 2021

Context/Funding:

GSRT (Greek General Secretariat for Research and Technology)

HEADSTART KETs

V2X communication, positioning

HEADSTART contact

ICCS

Description:

In the AVINT project, participating partners will study the urban transport context in Trikala city and will implement a bus line supported by automated buses in a full integration mode with the city transport network. The specific bus line will provide a viable service for the city interconnecting the city centre with the Sport Science university campus. To accomplish this, AVINT will perform all the necessary tasks: feasibility study, implementation study, infrastructure adaptation, renting and adaptation of automated buses prior to coordination of pilot tests. The pilot results will be thoroughly analysed with regard to their impact on the Trikala traffic. AVINT will also examine the system expansion in the City of Trikala and will provide a Roadmap to implementation in other Greek cities.

Link:

<https://avint-project.eu/index.php/en/>

3.5.5 General assessment of HEADSTART requirements collection

This use case mostly depends on V2X communication and positioning. Very important aspects are to keep constant communication to the control centre which monitors the automated route and the proper positioning within the documented route. High throughput and low latency are again needed to ensure valid communication. The main challenge is to ensure reliable infrastructural conditions throughout the route and continuously monitor the quality of service.

4 Use cases: Relevance ranking

This chapter gives an overview of the assembled material and a relevance ranking of the investigated use cases. As mentioned, HEADSTART will validate and demonstrate the methodology by applying it on up to four use cases which should allow both physical and model-based testing, as well as testing of the three identified KETs (positioning, communication, cybersecurity). The aspects of consumer testing, type approval and consumer testing should be considered for the selection, as well as feasibility in terms of project length and confidentiality issues.

In order to ensure an informed selection of use cases to be given more attention within the project a survey has also been conducted to complement the existing material; the results of this survey are included in this chapter.

As neither use case definitions nor technology will be developed within HEADSTART, the approach taken to compile the resources will be conducting a review of the available work done for each different use case.

4.1 Ranking Method

A ranking of the use cases investigated in Section 3 has been performed. The method chosen for taking the various sources of gathered data into consideration was to ask a number of experts within the HEADSTART project to use their domain knowledge and expertise to rank the use cases in a number of dimensions. The experts' task was to rank the suitability of each use case cross-referenced with each requirement category.

We are at step 3 in the approach arrive at the ranked list described in chapter 1, namely the task of assess in each use case in terms of its ability to meet the requirements identified for the project.

To that end, they were asked to take the following information into account when answering the questions:

- General requirements for KETs (see Chapter 4 in the deliverable 1.3 "Compiled functional and technical requirements for KETs").
- Information about the use cases (see Chapter 3 "Use cases: Definitions and availability" in the deliverable 1.4).
- The general project requirements on use cases (see Chapter 2 "Requirements on use cases in HEADSTART" in the deliverable 1.4).
- The detailed requirements on use cases, are stored in an excel file with a snapshot of the document is available as Annex 1.

The results are shown in Section below, and an aggregated suitability ranking based on the individual dimensions is shown in Section 5.

4.2 Results of suitability of use cases cross-referenced to requirements.

The figures in this subchapter show is the specific result for within each category, for the general project requirements on use cases and categories (see Chapter 2 “Requirements on use cases in HEADSTART” in the deliverable 1.4).

FIGURE 11: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH POSITIONING

FIGURE 12: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH COMMUNICATION

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 13: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH CYBERSECURITY

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 14: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH PHYSICAL TESTING

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 15: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH PROVING GROUND TESTING

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 16: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH FIELD OPERATIONAL TESTS

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 17: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED TO REQUIREMENTS WITH MODEL-BASED TESTING

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 18: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED WITH AVAILABILITY OF SCENARIOS

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 19: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED WITH COLLABORATION PARTNERS

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 20: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED WITH RELEVANCE TO OEMS AND TIER1'S

■ Highly Suitable
 ■ Suitable
 ■ Not Suitable

FIGURE 21: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED WITH TYPE APPROVAL AUTHORITIES

FIGURE 22: SUITABILITY OF USE CASES CROSS-REFERENCED WITH CONSUMER TESTING

5 Conclusions and implications

The HEADSTART project proposal initially identified four use cases; “truck platooning”, “highway pilot”, “rural road” and “urban driving”. Other use cases like “robot taxi” and “urban automated shuttle” have also been discussed during the initial phase of the project. For consistence, the ERTRAC five identified use cases (Truck platooning, Highway Pilot, Traffic Jam Chauffeur, Valet Parking and Urban Automated Shuttle) have been used as a reference in this and previous deliverables.

This deliverable has summarised use cases and functions of different scenarios. When applicable, environmental aspects such as road conditions and country specific issues are addressed. We conclude that techniques and methods for verification or validation have a real need not be develop, expanded and harmonized.

OEMs indicated that their main interests are in the use cases “traffic jam chauffeur” and “highway chauffeur/pilot” (both use cases at SAE levels 3 and 4). Other interesting use cases could be “valet parking” and “low speed shuttles” [17]

- Policy makers prioritize “highway lane keeping” followed by “highway pilot with lane changes”. [17]
- Research institutes have interest in “highway driving/pilot”, “traffic jam chauffeur”, “urban driving functions”, “truck platooning” and “valet parking” [17]

In order to validate and demonstrate the methodology HEADSTART will apply it to up to four use cases, so a reduction of the number of use cases is a must, and to provide the best informational foundation for that selection is the purpose of this deliverable. The task is to make a suitability ranking for the 5 use cases with respect to the criteria of representativeness to the project purpose in the aspects of:

- Development testing
- Type approval
- Consumer testing
- Positioning
- Communication
- Cybersecurity

This has been accomplished by the following approach:

1. Identify and compile the requirements that a use case must fulfil to demonstrate the HEADSTART methodology. The general project requirements on use cases can be found in Chapter 2 “Requirements on use cases in HEADSTART” in this deliverable. The detailed requirements on use cases, are stored in an excel file and a snapshot of the document is available as Annex 1.
2. Starting from the list of use cases indicated as priorities in the surveys and interviews produced in *Task 1.2 – Stakeholders and user group needs*, compile a detailed description of each use case can be found in Chapter 3 “Use cases: Definitions and availability” in this deliverable.
 - a. A description of the use case
 - b. A list of available resources, including projects that cover the use case and their status.
3. The Assessment for each use case in terms of its ability to meet the requirements identified for the project can be found in Chapter 4 “Use cases: Relevance ranking” in this deliverable.
4. The compilation of the assessments from Chapter 4 “Use cases: Relevance ranking” of the use cases rank in terms of suitability for HEADSTART project can be seen below in Figure 23. This ranking is predicated on the information that is available at the present time and is subject to change due to the fast evolution of the connected and automated driving R&D arena.

	Truck Platooning	Highway Pilot	Traffic Jam Chauffeur	Valet Parking	Urban Automated Shuttle
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements on testability of positioning in HEADSTART	● 3.8	● 3.6	● 2.6	● 4.3	● 4.5
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements on testability of communication in HEADSTART	● 4.8	● 3.4	● 1.9	● 3.5	● 3.5
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements of testability of cyber-security in HEADSTART	● 4.5	● 3.1	● 2.4	● 3.7	● 3.7
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding physical testing in HEADSTART	● 4.3	● 4.3	● 3.5	● 4.3	● 2.9
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding proving-ground testing in HEADSTART	● 4.1	● 3.6	● 3.1	● 3.8	● 2.6
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding field operational tests in HEADSTART	● 4.0	● 4.1	● 3.4	● 3.8	● 3.1
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding model-based testing in HEADSTART	● 3.9	● 3.6	● 3.6	● 3.9	● 3.6
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding definition and availability of scenarios in HEADSTART	● 3.3	● 3.8	● 3.5	● 3.0	● 2.6
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding requirements on collaboration partners in HEADSTART	● 4.0	● 3.7	● 2.9	● 3.3	● 2.6
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to OEMs and Tier1's in HEADSTART.	● 3.0	● 4.8	● 4.5	● 3.5	● 3.3
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to type-approval authorities in HEADSTART	● 3.3	● 4.1	● 3.9	● 2.8	● 2.9
How suitable is the use case to meet the requirements regarding relevance to consumer testing in HEADSTART	● 1.7	● 3.9	● 3.6	● 2.4	● 1.7
Total Average Score	3.7	3.8	3.2	3.5	3.1

FIGURE 23: AGGREGATED SUITABILITY RANKING OF THE 5 USE CASES

Based on the user needs identified at this stage in the project, and on the premise that all aspects are equality important, it seems reasonable to focus our efforts on the following use cases in the following order:

- Highway Pilot
- Truck Platooning
- Valet Parking
- Traffic Jam Chauffeur
- Urban Automated Shuttle

The definition of a use case including all scenarios and functions requires thorough effort. The HEADSTART project has decided not to make its own definitions of use cases in the project, but to apply use case specifications by other research initiatives and industrial cooperation.

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Annex 1: Detailed requirements on use cases from HEADSTART

Living document (excel file) version 53 input.

Category	Requirement	Explanatory text
Testability of KETs - Communication	Some functions in the operational layer shall depend on communication	To enable testing of KET - communication, the function must utilize communication. Since the focus in HEADSTART is on the operational layer, the communication usage must be in the operational layer.
Model-based testing	CAD-function: Functional description (may include Tactical maneuvers, ODD elements, ...)	Necessary information to evaluate the CAD-function
Model-based testing	CAD-function as code (for SiL/MiL) and on target HW (ECU) (for HiL)	Necessary information from the CAD-function for SiL/MiL/HiL
Model-based testing	Sensors: Sensor setup (field of view from all the sensors & sensor positions on VUT)	Necessary for the sensor model in simulation
Model-based testing	Sensors: Object list based feedback from the driven scenarios of the VUT	Necessary if only the CAD-function should be evaluated (to distinguish between errors from the sensor suite)
Model-based testing	Sensors: GPS data from VUT during scenario (for KET positioning)	For evaluation of GPS data quality and for correlation between PG and simulation.
Model-based testing	Sensors: For probabilistic sensor models: statistical failure rates	Necessary for the respective sensor model in simulation
Model-based testing	Sensors: For physical sensor models: detailed knowledge of the respective sensor properties	Necessary for the respective sensor model in simulation
Model-based testing	Vehicle dynamics: Mass / dimensions / Centre of gravity/ (Moment of inertia for z-axis) of VUT	Necessary for the vehicle model in simulation

Category	Requirement	Explanatory text
Model-based testing	Vehicle dynamics: Minimal vehicle dynamics measurements: Exact position (with D-GPS) and orientation	Necessary for the vehicle model in simulation
Model-based testing	Vehicle dynamics measurements from scenarios (and/or basic scenarios) including lateral & longitudinal acceleration, steering wheel angle, pedal positions	Accompanying the verification of the vehicle model used in simulations with PG results. The necessity of this requirement is highly dependent on the actual maneuvers executed by the CAD function.
Model-based testing	Vehicle dynamics: VUT on test bench (for ViL)	Necessary for ViL approach
Model-based testing	Virtual Environment - Static: OpenDRIVE description for the scenario (including potential special conditions on PG)	Necessary for the virtual environment in simulation
Model-based testing	Virtual Environment - Dynamic: OpenSCENARIO description (of the scenario to be tested on PG and for virtual testing)	Necessary for the virtual environment in simulation
Testability of KETs - Cyber Security	Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) activity to be carried out as part of the cybersecurity lifecycle (involving the CAD-function of the VUT).	Cybersecurity testing highly depends on actions to be done in the design phase of a vehicle or vehicle function. One very important analysis in this aspect is the Threat Analysis and Risk Assessment (TARA) activity to be carried out as part of the cybersecurity lifecycle.
Testability of KETs - Cyber Security	Addressing key cyber threats identified by the UN Task Force on Cyber Security and Over-the-Air Issues of the Working Party on Automated/Autonomous and Connected Vehicles (GRVA) within the World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations (WP.29)	Automated vehicles are prone to many different threats. These threats can be grouped in many ways. It is important that you can systematically cover all threats and that you do not risk of missing some. Therefore, HEADSTART will follow standardized cyber-security threat catalogues available in literature.

Category	Requirement	Explanatory text
Requirements on collaboration partners	Making arrangements with other projects	Making formal arrangements with other projects.
Requirements on collaboration partners	Sharing test data & results	Allowance of other projects to share test data & results with HEADSTART.
Requirements on collaboration partners	Availability of use case till end 2021	Availability of use case till end of HEADSTART for final event (end 2021).
Physical Testing - proving ground	Easy repainting of the lanes	Sometimes, to test a specific case of a function it is necessary to change the width of the lane or to draw a specific geometry (e.g. different radius of turning), which implies that new lanes must be painted.
Physical Testing - proving ground	Imitate/mimic methodologic situations (e.g. lateral wind)	There are functions that react when an adverse meteorological phenomenon occurs.
Relevance to key user groups - Type approval	The technical documentation provided by the OEM must be well described. The limits of the operational domain of the function must be accurate so it is easy to identify the most relevant cases or worst test to test.	In some cases, if a specific test cannot be practically achieved due to e.g. the limitations of the test facilities, with the consent of the type approval authority be fulfilled through the use of documentation. For this reason, the documentation provided must be complete and accurate.
Relevance to key user groups - Type approval	The test track of the proving ground must be easy to change e.g. (different lane geometries)	According to the tests requirements of the most advanced functionalities that can be type-approved nowadays, the test conditions and the vehicle test speed shall be within the operating range of the system. This means that you may need to adapt the test track or the testing area to the system that you are evaluating. Also the new lay-out of the lanes used in the testing must be reported with the test results.

Category	Requirement	Explanatory text
Relevance to key user groups - Type approval	Technical Service and OEM must go together during the development phase.	Accompaniment in the development phases to ensure the fulfilment of the functional safety requirements (e.g. SOTIF, ISO 26262, etc.).
Physical Testing - Field operational tests	Driver impact and impact of other road users need to be taken into account	Impact of driver behaviour (driver override, take-over) should be recorded/reported as well as behaviour of other road users (other drivers, pedestrians, etc.).
Relevance to key user groups - Type approval	Suitable Test-Tools need to be available	Test-Tools (synchronized and repeatable testing with multiple vehicle targets, other road users (e.g. VRU)) must be robust and available on proving grounds.
Physical Testing - Field operational tests	Baseline-Condition needs to be defined	System behaviour needs to be compared to baseline condition, this needs to be defined prior to the test (SAE L0, L1 or L2).
Physical Testing - Field operational tests	Testing conditions need to be defined	Test conditions (road type, infrastructure, traffic, weather, etc.) should be standardized to allow comparison between different vehicles.
Relevance to key user groups - Consumer testing	HMI, ODD or Comfort assessment instead of safety assessment	Since safety is ensured by type approval, typical consumer testing should focus on other criteria.
Relevance to key user groups - Type approval	Full system functionality must be available on proving ground	Because of geo-fencing (required by type approval), it is important to ensure that all kinds of intended system functionalities are available and testable on proving grounds.
Relevance to key user groups - Consumer testing	Safety benefit of the function	For consumer testing the use case should have a clear safety benefit on road injuries
Relevance to key user groups - Consumer testing	Minimum risk manoeuvre implemented in the function logic	MRM should address risky situations in case of driver unavailability (L4-5)
Physical Testing - proving ground	Targets allowed maximum impact speed above the tested scenarios speed	Scenarios should address realistic situations and parameters of the use case

Category		Requirement	Explanatory text
Testability of KETs - Communication	of -	Infrastructures available for V2I communication	If V2I communication is required by the function, check availability of communication infrastructures in proving ground or public road.
Testability of KETs - Communication	of -	Low latency and high reliability should apply in the V2X communications	Conformance, function and performance testing should support the V2X communications providing among others interoperability, high performance and reliability
Testability of KETs - Communication	of -	Ensure security in V2X communications	Perform gateway, penetration and accelerated testing to ensure secure V2X communications
Testability of KETs - Cyber Security	of -	Models/tools available to rank cybersecurity	Explore existing toolkits (either commercial or not) or models to rank cybersecurity, using a generic well-defined parameterized approach
Definition and availability of scenarios	and of	We need to have recorded scenarios available from a database meeting the requirements regarding especially ODD but also in terms of scenario concept	
Definition and availability of scenarios	and of	We need a scenario concept which is aligned with the overall methodology and which supports especially the required ODD	
Definition and availability of scenarios	and of	The scenario concept and the available scenarios need to cover all the required layers (1-6) which have an impact on the use case and therefore need to be regarded when it comes to testing	

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